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Message from the Editor

This is the second issue of Sinology Journal of University of Würzburg. First, I want to express special gratitude to all the editors who worked tirelessly to make this issue possible, in particular York Frerks and Aleksandra Tuchkova, for their hard work and scrupulous editing in every round. Second, I am so grateful to our professors in the Chinese Studies department for all the help and support, as well as their feedback for the first issue, which helped us to improve the quality of our work. Finally, special thanks to all the authors for their trust in our journal, all the hard work and cooperation with our editors.

It has been a long road, and I am very proud that we realized our ideas regarding this issue. We diversified the variety of topics, with new articles on Chinese Policy and Ideology, Art, and Literature. Hopefully this will be just the beginning of a good tradition in our students' society in Würzburg and will help to engage with Sinology student societies from all over the world.

“Place Branding in a Chinese County: How Diaspora Discourse is Applied to Urban Development”

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Abstract: This study examines how Qingtian County integrates diaspora heritage into its urban development strategies. By examining local policies and development projects, the paper highlights how collective diaspora identity intersects with China's modernisation efforts. Key findings reveal the governments' efforts to integrate diaspora legacies into urban development planning, through place branding strategy to create a competitive image based on selected features, yet some other policies and practices are problematic and contradictory.

Keywords: place branding, diaspora politics, Overseas Chinese Hometown, urbanisation in PRC

1. Introduction

China has progressively incorporated diaspora policies to leverage overseas Chinese for economic development, nation-building, and political support (H. Liu and Dongen 2016; Thunø 2018). Human capital flight and outflow of the working-age population are major concerns related to outward migration. The implementation of politically motivated programs aims to attract Chinese back to China (Goodkind 2019: 15). Overseas Hometown (侨乡)¹ is an important concept to create a collective identity, sense of belonging and emphasise the unique role and contribution of the Chinese diaspora (Barabantseva 2011:114). Scholars have been exploring diasporic place-making and its implications for China's global governance aspirations, examining it through the new trends of diaspora roles on domestic and international stages (Thunø 2018; Liu 2022; Masdeu 2015; C. Wang 2017; Bofulin 2022a; Bofulin 2022b). In recent years, there has been a new trend of creating international city branding in Overseas Hometowns (Liu 2022). This research attempts to shed light on the Overseas Hometown urban development from the lens of place branding. The local governments steering national policies and place branding of Overseas Hometown becomes a strategic measure that can align or conflict with higher-level directives. By analyzing the development projects of the urban plan for Qingtian, this case study this paper attempts to answer the following question: How do local governments use and reconstruct diaspora heritage in place branding urban development?

¹ Localities with outward migration tendencies.

This study commences with an examination of the theoretical principles underpinning place branding, with a particular focus on its application within the context of China's urbanization initiatives. Subsequently, the discourse surrounding the Chinese diaspora is examined, with particular attention to the process of romanticization of international migration. In particular, the Chinese government has historically and continues to make efforts to create diasporic urban spaces, which are often manifested through the objects of westernization. Thematic analysis of data from policy documents allows for an examination of key themes, including characteristic township development, highway interconnections, the overseas Chinese economy as a business model, and a tourist resort. It is noteworthy that the recent relocation of cemeteries and tombs for development and renovation purposes appears to be at odds with the preservation of diaspora heritage and ancestral legacies. In summary, the overseas hometown cases provide insights into the challenges and opportunities of transforming a labor-exporting area into a capitalized urban space with diaspora heritage as its defining feature. While this study is based on a review of media articles and policy documentation and has research limitations, there are sufficient materials to understand the government's vision for the ideal Overseas Hometown.

2. Place Branding as Urbanisation Strategy

Place branding entails the reinvention of places through a process of brand construction, which promotes individual or collective identities; it aims to attract investment and human capital, compete in the tourism industry, and encourage citizens to identify with the place where they live. More importantly, this is intended to stimulate the economy and boost social development and, consequently, the economy (San Eugenio Vela et al. 2023:2; Cavia 2011:107). The goal of the branding is not limited to transmitting and communicating an image to the outside audience. The differentiation between collective and individual identities "specifically works with the local population to increase their pride in their home and the feeling of belonging to a certain place" (Kalandides 2012; San Eugenio Vela 2023). From an urban government perspective, place branding can be seen as a form of economic development competition. Local and regional governments compete in the marketplace by actively shaping how their place is perceived by potential consumers (Cleave and Gilliland 2016:208-209; Pasquinelli 2013 2013:2-3).

In 2014, the State Council of the PRC released the "National New-Type Urbanization Plan" (国家新型城镇化规划, hereafter NUP) as a guideline for implementing urban development policies. NUP's objectives widely range from urban-rural integration, population control,

hukou reform, social welfare system, public service provision, green and sustainable development, and preservation of local culture, to coordinated development among different regions (Thünken 2020:59-61). NUP differentiates the responsibilities of the central, provincial, and local governments (Griffiths and Schiavone 2016:73-91, C. Wang 2020:275). NUP has an additional agenda to promote a shift in China's economic strategy to boost domestic consumption, the service sector, and the global connectivity of inland cities (Chu 2020:4). The plan prioritizes the Citizenisation of migrant workers, moving from rural areas to small and medium towns, to balance demographic and economic distribution.

Citizenisation (市民化), or transfer from rural to urban residence, is a crucial element in the narrative of society's evolution from agricultural to urban and industrial forms and a key feature of Chinese modernization (Mobrand 2015:110). The rural-urban transfer is regulated by a "differentiated settlement policy," which categorizes cities according to type and population size and prioritizes migration flows towards small and medium-sized (satellite) ones. This classification determines each entity's varying settlement requirements and restrictions (Thünken 2020:318). Counties are important linkages in rural-urban integration that connect and govern villages and towns. Rural-urban integration is sometimes achieved by merging villages or incorporating them into townships within the county (Qingtian Government 2024 n.p). Due to mass migration, many villages have become empty or populated, mainly by "left-behind children" and the elderly. These villages are also common in Qingtian (Xu Hui 2021).

Despite the persistent rural-urban divide, the urban lifestyle holds significant appeal for many. However, some individuals hesitate to change their residential status (hukou) from rural to urban. Their primary concern is the potential loss of valuable rural assets, such as contract land (承包地) and housing land (宅基地), which they perceive as outweighing the benefits of city life (C. Chen and Fan 2016). At the same time, rural hukou is regarded as a safety net for migrant workers who constantly travel between cities and villages (Hu 2023:1839). Chan concludes that China's hukou reform has stalled and failed to address the growing social disparities and challenges migrant populations face, particularly concerning access to education for children (Chan 2021). The hybrid identity of transnational Overseas Chinese and governmental efforts to integrate rural and urban spaces are erasing these hukou boundaries, which is both challenging and advantageous for steering urban and diaspora policies.

3. Challenges of Urban Development

Qingtian faces several challenges that hinder urban development and Shiminhua, including environmental conditions, a high proportion of senior citizens, out-migration, and the mobility of its residents. The area is mostly mountainous and has several rivers that belong to the Ou River system and benefit from abundant water resources (Chen 1990:122). Tea plants blanket the region, characterizing and contributing significantly to the economy and livelihoods (Liu et al. 2021:472). The county meets the conditions for a protective type zone and is not suitable for development expansion or population growth, and requires strict control on nature protection (Wang et al. 2017:4-5). The Qingtian region has a favorable ecological environment, but its mountainous terrain limits urban expansion, yet the county is nevertheless promoted for urban expansion and development (Data n.d. n.p.; LCDRC 2022: 85; Lishui Shi Tongjiju, 2023:26). The permanent population is relatively small, which reduces the population burden. In 2021, the population was 570,500, a slight decrease from 572,311 in 2020. From 2020 to 2023, the region was observed to have negative population growth due to outward labor migration. The region's total area is 2,477 square kilometers (Data n.d. n.p.). The proportion of elderly residents in Qingtian in 2020 was 18.1 percent, slightly lower than the average Lishui (20.35 percent) and national levels, yet the population merely increased in the last 20 years. The urbanization rate is one of the lowest at the county level in Lishui and has remained as low as 50 percent in the past five years (Lishui City Bureau of Statistics, 2023 n.p. and 2024 n.p.; CEIC DATA n.p.; Government 2022 n.p.). The rapid economic growth and constant influx of migrants have led to severe social issues and an unbalanced demographic configuration (Thunoe, 1996; Zhang 2007; Masdeu 2019). For many years, the export of labor was the main source of finance, and later, the practice of migration was praised as a heroic act of loyalty and a development path.

3.1 Background of Overseas Hometown Economy

The identity of Overseas Hometowns is deeply rooted in their history, geopolitics, and economy, which have collectively shaped a model of migrant economy. This model has been further reinforced by the subtle romanticizing of migration legacies, influencing both the incentives for migration and the processes involved. As part of this dynamic, diaspora policies have been strategically steered by intertwining romanticized narratives with cosmopolitan ideals. Consequently, the positive narrative surrounding migrant legacies has been elevated to an ideal concept, particularly in the Qingtian urban space context.

The networking culture among Overseas Chinese facilitates economic development in Zhejiang province and, on a greater scale, serves as a starting point for the province's integration with the global economy (Rabe 2022:124-125). However, while migrants' remittances and donations have contributed to economic and urban sustenance, the lack of investment in production and job opportunities was discouraging potential investors (Zhang 2007:74-75). Qingtian may not be as prosperous as other 'migration hometowns' of Wenzhou or Xiamen, localities with outward migration tendencies.

Yow distinguishes three economic development models for Overseas Chinese Hometowns: foreign-investment-driven, capital-lacking, and donation-supported. When overseas Chinese heavily donated to their hometown infrastructure in Guangdong and Zhejiang before 1949, the period was characterized as donation-supported. After the economic reform in 1978, the migrants channeled productive foreign investment flow for the industries, which became a prominent receiver of financing, which is why this period is labeled as being in a foreign-investment-driven mode. While some hometowns flourished, others could not overcome the challenges of remoteness and rurality, later losing their kinship links and becoming capital-lacking districts. The capitalized economies arose from foreign direct investment in light manufacturing, household, and private enterprises that used remittance circulation (Yow 2007: 84-85, 98-102). Some similar patterns are observed in Qingtian in space-time dimensions, where familial kinship pushed financing, and political and economic reforms stimulated investment (Masdeu 2019:5). The migrant economy peaked between 1988-2007 when remittances increased by 20 percent annually and encouraged the trade and tourism sectors to become major resources for economic development (Committee 2013:560-563).

Zhang Xiumig concludes that Qingtian's economic growth was outstanding among other counties in the early 2000s and urban areas of Hecheng district, Wenxi, and Chuang Liao towns (鹤城区, 温溪镇, 船寮镇) naturally became industrial and international trade zones (Zhang 2007:72). However, the financial flow did not create conditions for sustainable development, because the incoming donations were primarily allocated to private consumption and real estate of the dependent families. In 2002, Qingtian was one of the most underdeveloped counties in the province, and working outside was one of the few career options available to villagers (Zhang 2007:78-80).

Over time, the government has leveraged the migration legacy and network to attract foreign direct investment and alleviate poverty in regions with Overseas Chinese Hometowns (Yow

2007; Bofulin 2021). The Lishui government recognized and analyzed the contribution of migrant workers and proposed development strategies to integrate their economy into regional policies. An article in the Zhejiang Ribao Gazette sends a message about government cooperation with migrant workers for better development. In 2001, in cooperation with the city government, the Lishui Municipal Commission proposed development strategies to integrate the "migrant economy" into regional policies.

"Qingtian has achieved leapfrog development. The industrial economy is the main force, and the overseas Chinese economy is the driving force."

青田实现跨越式发展，工业经济是主力，华侨经济是动力 (Zhejiang Today, 2002:38-39)

The government has supported outward migration as a strategy for domestic development, particularly through the 'Overseas Chinese Talent Return Project' (华侨要素回流工程) initiated in 2001. This initiative led to the establishment of a "Leading Group for Overseas Chinese Affairs," which simplifies passport procedures and addresses educational reintegration challenges for returning Chinese children. The government enhanced services such as paperwork processing and travel arrangements to assist the diaspora further. Additionally, a subsidy of 5,000 yuan per person was introduced to encourage low-income residents to work abroad, significantly boosting interest in overseas employment (Li, Wangming 2011:35).

The establishment of the "Investment Pool" (项目投资库) and the "Overseas Chinese Returning Home Investors Association" (华侨回乡投资者协会) has streamlined the process of attracting foreign investment by providing timely project information. These efforts have fostered the growth of foreign trade and advanced the concept of the "headquarters economy." To strengthen ties with the diaspora, the government launched the "Qingtian Overseas Network" (青田侨网) and publishes the "Qingtian Overseas Hometown News" (青田侨乡报), creating communication platforms that keep overseas Chinese connected with their hometown. Additionally, the government supports elderly returnees and maintains strong relations with overseas Chinese communities, hosting a biennial Overseas Chinese Conference to further these connections.

"Encourage low-income people to carry forward the Qingtian spirit of daring to explore and daring to take risks."

鼓励低收入群众发扬敢闯敢冒的青田精神 (Li, Wangming 2011:35-36)

Chinese scholar Li Wangming, in research on urbanization in Qingtian, positively describes the impact of migration and government engagement with the diaspora on urban development. "Qingtian spirit" implies the motivation to escape poverty, take control of one's own life, take risks and delve into the unknown, help the diaspora community and the dependent family, endure struggles of work and a new place of living, and, most importantly, achieve success as an international entrepreneur. Qingtian government shared an article with a similar connotation, stressing the qualities of the Overseas Chinese. Together, these qualities form the narrative of collective identity and the ideal image of the diaspora.

"The overseas Chinese... have cultivated the Qingtian overseas Chinese cultural spirit characterized by' daring to venture, having a global vision; enduring hardship, being simple and honest; uniting in mutual assistance, valuing affection and righteousness; being sincere and kind, willing to contribute; striving hard, pioneering and advancing; loving the motherland and hometown, cherishing the homeland and roots."

侨华人...形成了“敢闯敢冒、放眼全球；吃苦耐劳、质朴敦厚；团结互助、重情尚义；至诚和善、乐于奉献；勇于拼搏、开拓奋进；爱国爱乡，恋祖恋土”的青田华侨文化精神 (People's Daily 2014 n.p.).

The examples mentioned above show idealistically reflected diaspora collective identities throughout the time. The government has romanticized the legacy of migration and encouraged people to follow in the footsteps of previous generations who escaped poverty and carried the burden of their community's survival in the region. The motivation behind supporting migrants is to attract investment from wealthy diasporas, which serves as the country's primary source of financing, thereby contributing to the migrant economy (Benton and Gomez 2014:1163). As they narrate, "set up convenient service windows for the people in counties and towns" (在各县镇设立便民服务窗口) (Zhejiang Today 2002:39). To sustain itself, the migrant economy model relies on the establishment of specific values and concepts, including diasporic place-making.

Qingtian immigrants arrived as unskilled labor workers to fulfill the emerging needs of the fashion industry in Italy and Spain in 1980-2000. Factories often hired entire groups of migrants through their village connections (Lan and S. Zhu 2014b). Networking between Chinese and Overseas Chinese in Italy stimulated the trade of materials and finished products between the two countries (Ceccagno 2012). Ideally, migrants would change their status from hiring workers to starting trade or restaurant businesses. This transition is made possible by accessing capital and discovering new opportunities while relying on an established community network. For rural immigrants, migration is costly and often involves repaying debts during the initial period (Ottati and Cologna 2015:38-40). Many workers extend their

working hours to acquire financial capital, repay debts, and further develop their businesses, often without breaks or holidays (Lan and S. Zhu 2014a:155).

In 2011, Latham and B. Wu conducted fieldwork in Europe and found that income inequalities in China, reflected in social stratification and labor market segregation, have influenced economic and social structures in Overseas Chinese communities in Europe. This has led to poor working conditions and even forced labor practices in some European Chinese businesses (Latham and B. Wu 2013:23, 45-46). Traveling to Europe from China was often facilitated via developed routes of human trafficking, common in the 1990s and early 2000s. However, illegal migration declined in the late 2000s (Latham and B. Wu 2013:23-24). Despite the tragedy of international migration, often driven by poverty, most migrant workers who travel across the globe have more bitter memories than nostalgia. The government-led discourse on Overseas Chinese and their hometowns has long been romanticized, interpreting their experiences as heroic sacrifices and paths to success.

3.2 Romanticising International Migration and Europeanisation of Urban Space

Zhu and Maags identify five stages in the heritage process: institutionalization, authentication, recognition, museumization, and commercialization. Through 'value appropriation,' cultural sites and practices are selected and transformed into public and private goods. Chinese heritage legislation provides a legal basis and spreads selected practices and heritage discourses vertically, mediated by official heritage institutions. The authorities and experts then select the cultural themes and objects that have the potential to become representative and receive formal recognition (Y. Zhu and Maags 2020:128-141).

Heritage discourse serves as a powerful narrative that frames the elite's involvement in rural revitalization as a preservation of cultural tradition, masking the underlying economic and social power dynamics. This discourse legitimizes their dominance in rural governance by positioning the "New Gentry" as protectors and promoters of heritage. It justifies the privatization of resources and land that primarily benefits the elite. The new gentry select social elites select nostalgic memories and aspects of traditional cultural revitalization to match the demands of contemporary social transformation and diversified aesthetic expressions (Tao, P. Chen, and Aoki 2024:50).

Historically, Overseas Chinese have been the main financial fuel for urban development (Zhang 2007). However, some scholars argue that the diasporic community itself had an insignificant influence on the contemporary state-led diasporic place-making process for their migrant

hometowns and other "international cities" (国际化城市) (Liu 2022). Urban diasporic-space-making is a deliberate process of capitalizing on migrant resources to conceptualize urban development, westernization, and social transformation from agrarian communities to capitalist societies, infused with diasporic values and migration heritage (Liu 2022: 212, 209-227). China approaches the conceptualization of the urban heritage industry as a form of theatre, where cultural spectacles are curated through museumification, documentation, and ritualization to evoke sensations of awe and nostalgia (C. Wang 2017). Local governments attempt to integrate the transnationalism of diaspora into cosmopolitan practices by staging performances for external audiences (Jamec 2023). Qingtian's identity, shaped by the romanticizing of migration history and Europeanisation, serves the national goal of and enhances its regional competitiveness through a blend of modernity and diasporic values (Bofulin 2022a: 390-392).

The narratives of international Overseas Hometowns are strategically constructed through the interaction of socio-political actors alongside cosmopolitan and consumerist agendas to justify social transformation. Perceptions, narratives, and practices in the case study locality reflect aspirations for internationalization as a path to socio-economic development, transforming a rural agrarian society into an urban and capitalized one. Chinese diaspora discourse is dominated by heroism and cosmopolitan themes, where the idealized image of successful and loyal returnees aligns with government-led agendas (Jamec 2023:61, 63). International cosmopolitanism is reflected in objects of Western food consumption and branded product availability, which market consumerist attitudes as part of the appreciation of urban life. Jamec proposes a re-understanding of one of the representations of transnationalism — coffee consumption culture—and discusses the bitterness of the overseas migrant's experience.

In Mingxi County, the government initiated a Coffee Room to promote coffee culture consumption as a cosmopolitan curiosity for tourists. However, an attempt to capitalize on crafted heritage subjects has failed. Jamec explains that locals adopt coffee culture, but more as a casual and individual habit rather than a social one. In contrast, tea drinking is considered and practiced as a more ceremonial and community event. While Qingtian, coffee is represented as a symbol of cosmopolitanism (Bofulin 2016), in Mingxi, coffee drinking is not. Jamec argues that "coffee consumption is forced upon the body" because migrants have been drinking low-cost coffee to endure tiredness and hardship during long hours in detrimental working conditions. This example may seem insignificant, but alongside other themes of hard-

earned success abroad, financial contributions to the hometown, and international and educated migrants, the discourse shapes a highly idealized image of the diaspora.

This approach neglects and ignores the dark side of the migrants' experience. News articles from China News and other popular platforms present identical storytelling on Qingtian migrant communities (China News 2023 n.p.; 163.com n.p.). The media portrayal of Qingtian highlights its remarkable transformation from a once impoverished county to an economically prosperous and internationally connected area. Qingtian's development is frequently depicted through the lens of its migrant economy and the internationalization that modernized the county, elevating it to the status of a "top ten county." (163.com n.p.) Articles from China News emphasize Qingtian's economic success by comparing South European townships and describing the growth of an internationalized market as a testament to its prosperity (China News 2023 n.p.). Additionally, a video from the popular platform 163.com not only traces the history of Qingtianese migration but also addresses the challenges arising from ongoing migration, such as empty villages and the increase in left-behind elderly and children. With emotional interviews with lonely seniors and minors and images of empty houses, the video evokes mixed feelings and narrates its vision of the past and present of rural areas.

"Qingtian's economic disparity and lack of emotion, magnified by the exchange rate and distance, has long been hidden under the booming so-called overseas Chinese economy."

青田这份被汇率和距离无限放大的经济落差与情感却位长久的掩盖在繁荣蓬勃的华侨经济下 (163.com n.p.).

The video is structured to show the progress and transformation on regional and national levels. Ultimately, the migrant economy is framed as a product of bravery that shook off the poverty.

"Two hundred years ago, the courage to leave the mountains allowed the Qingtian people to escape poverty. And the courage to go home two hundred years later allowed the people of Qingtian to find the answers..."

... 两百年前从山区走出国门的勇气让青田人拜托了贫困。而两百年后的回家的勇气让青田人找到答案... (163.com n.p.)

The key themes in these media sources are immigrants' hardships, close ties to Europe, attractiveness for foreign investment, economic success, and general competitiveness. Each of the articles introduces Qingtian as an exemplary country shaken by poverty, hardships, and struggles. It now enjoys a booming economy and a European urban lifestyle while needing its overseas youth. Perhaps it is exaggerated to make assumptions based on a few internet sources.

However, the positive side of the migrant legacy is highlighted in the different articles, coming from a long government-led Europeanisation process.

European style (欧洲式) is identified as "synonymous with a modern, sophisticated way of building or interior design." The foreign architectural design (洋楼) can be interpreted as the hallmark of Overseas Hometowns (Bofulin 2016:95). According to various media sources on Qingtian, such as China News 2023, News 2023, and 163.com n.p., the county is celebrated as the hometown of international, hardworking migrants who remain loyal to their roots. The urban space is full of European touches, there are cafe shops, western food, fine wine, and great choices for a shopping experience. An article from the Lishui Government indicates 2009 as the starting point for the renovation and westernization of urban spaces. The "international" layer of local identity is stated to increase the country's competitiveness (Lishui Government 2021 n.p.).

"Eight famous sculptures, including statues of Napoleon, David, and a bullfighter, have been installed along the road.... The "one core, two wings" urban space should strengthen the unique characteristics of the Overseas Chinese Hometown to stand out in regional competition."

沿路布设了拿破仑雕像、大卫雕像、斗牛士等 8 座著名雕塑。“一心两翼”城市空间，强化侨乡特色，才能在区域竞争中脱颖而出 (Lishui Government 2021 n.p.)

Interestingly, the traditional European style was interpreted as representing a universal and unified Europe, without specific reference to any particular epoch, culture, or region. At the same time, the internationalism of the overseas Chinese diaspora from Qingtian is no longer confined to Europe; instead, they have become increasingly transnational and mobile in recent years (Masdeu 2019). Another article emphasizes the influence of migrants and how it has enabled the country to synchronize with European cities and, consequently, global progress. The county aspires to become the "most beautiful county" of European style.

"The significant influence of overseas Chinese has shaped Qingtian into a distinctive" hometown of overseas Chinese," making it synchronized with world-renowned cities like Paris, Barcelona, Rome, and Milan. This influence allows Qingtian to keep pace with the world."

华侨的巨大影响，造就青田浓郁的侨乡特色，使得青田与巴黎、巴塞罗那、罗马、米兰等各国名城同步，与世界同步 (Qingtian Government 2021 n.p.)

The government has experimented with migration heritage not only as part of the architecture or a general town ambiance but also as a concept for commercial projects. One innovative

engagement with the diaspora is Qingtian's Imported Commodity City (ICC), which exemplifies how the ideas of diasporic urbanity can be materialized. In 2013, the Qingtian County Bureau of Commerce launched ICC, which includes specialized markets, an exhibition center, business services, and leisure tourism. Bofulin explains the intricate relationship between government, migration, and urbanization in the context of "cosmopolitanism through internationalization." In this regard, the local government employs the latest diaspora engagement strategies, leveraging the resources from emigration flows to transition the local economy from being a labor exporter to a service-oriented economy catering to domestic tourists. The ICC project "intended to function as a driver of future economic and urban transformation through internationalization" (Bofulin 2021:11)

This shift is reflected in the evolving diaspora mission, which aims to connect China with the world. The local government engages with the overseas Chinese via various activities, including legal affairs and public administration, investments, digital transformation, public diplomacy, and local urban restructuring (LCDRC 2022). The local economy is expected to transform from a labor exporter to a service-oriented economy for domestic tourists. The target audience consists of new returnees and Overseas Chinese who are visiting their hometown (Bofulin 2021:3). At the same time, the authorities are making efforts to fulfill the objectives of the national NUP and at the same time attract overseas talent to China, encouraging them to settle in urban areas and contribute to the process of urbanization and modernization (LCDRC 2022). Local governments leverage diaspora heritage and cultural narratives to enhance regional competitiveness and drive urban development. By integrating European-style aesthetics and promoting the legacy of overseas Chinese migrants, Qingtian has transformed into an "International County," showcasing a blend of modernity and constructed diaspora values.

4. Enhancing Place Image: Urban Development Planning

In 2022, the Lishui City Development and Reform Commission (丽水市发展和改革委员会, hereafter LCDRC) issued a localized urbanization plan for the region, detailing different guidelines, goals, and projects for Qingtian and other counties. The planning period spans from 2021 to 2025, with a perspective extended to 2035. The plan emphasizes urban demographic growth as an essential condition for further development. Under the leadership of the CPC

under Xi Jinping, Qingtian is expected to be revitalized as the local government implements policies, projects, and investments to make urban life in Qingtian more attractive.

The document begins by reviewing the achievements during the 13th Five-Year Plan (2016-2020), emphasizing significant progress in urbanization: population growth, urban integration, and improvements in infrastructure and services. The urban population increased, and urbanization exceeded 60 percent. Significant attention was given to the rural issues, to which the rural "Revitalisation Strategy" (乡村振兴战略) addresses its solutions, including population relocation, rural-urban integration, and others. Policies were implemented to integrate rural migrants into urban settings, including the large-scale relocation and rapid settlement" (大搬快治) program. Major improvements in urban infrastructure and public services, such as education, healthcare, and transportation, enhanced the quality of urban living (LCDRC 2022:1-4).

Under the provincial general strategy titled "Lishui to Build a Model City for New Urbanization in Mountainous Areas of the Country by 2035," the "Cross Mountain Integration" initiative serves as a local steering plan to fulfill the objectives of the NUP (LCDRC 2022:8). Citizenisation (shiminhua) measures include the integration of rural-to-urban migrant populations, simplification of the household registration process, and moving the villagers from mountainous areas to urban areas (Qingtian Government 2017 n.p.;LCDRC 2022:2, 19-20). The demolition of villages and graves is often seen as a necessary step to expand urban areas and relocate populations.

The plan is guided by Xi Jinping's thoughts on socialism with Chinese characteristics for a new era, touching upon high-quality green development, cross-mountain coordination, and Lishui's integration into the Yangtze River Delta Economic Belt. Basic principles of governance include strengthening the leading role of the central city, reshaping township patterns, integrating industries and cities, promoting urban-rural integration, balancing protection and innovation, and emphasizing efficient and intensive development. The plan aims to promote Lishui's rural urbanization, accelerate the construction of the "One Belt, Three Zones" development pattern, and establish Lishui as a model for new urbanization in mountainous areas of Zhejiang and across China.

The Lishui Plan outlines eleven projects designed to improve and foster communication, trade, technology, infrastructure, education, and healthcare sectors. (Appedix A) While a clear focus is on comprehensive development, a significant amount of investment is allocated to road

construction. The total investment is 370.27 billion RMB, with a significant proportion allocated for communication-related projects, amounting to 17.920 billion RMB, representing about 48.39 percent of the total budget. Other projects, including the Old City Core Area Renovation, Water Conservancy Hub, and Pumped Storage Power Station, may be categorized as infrastructure maintenance. These projects received another half, comprising about 16.455 billion RMB, equal to 48.39 percent. The public service sectors of healthcare and education received only about 4.46 percent of the total investment (LCDRC 2022:53-70, see Appendix A). Road construction aims to enhance mobility and create the conditions to accommodate an influx of people into smaller communities. Qingtian was given the 'Characteristic Township' as its development model, emphasizing its unique migration legacy, possible as this legacy is deeply intertwined with themes of transnationalism, modernity, success, and a connection to ancient ancestral roots. These themes are central to conceptualizing the county's economic and developmental activities, particularly in trade and tourism.

The Overseas Hometown can be constructed as a place brand by local socio-political actors, capitalizing on diasporic resources and reflections of globalization. The Overseas Chinese Hometown brand is a project under the Characteristic Towns initiative based on cosmopolitanism, internationalization, and modernity. The promotion of the diaspora legacy serves as an instrument for the construction of a unified nation and the fostering of a sense of belonging among local communities. This plan aligns with a broader national strategy of rural modernization and revitalization. Investment projects include regional intercommunication, infrastructure developments, and trade (LCDRC 2022: 14,19, 53-70). The local officials present the further development of Qingtian, which has emerged from a history of complex interactions between local actors and migrants, within the framework of the "Overseas Chinese Hometown city brand" (侨乡城镇品牌). Urban planning attempts to reflect diasporic heritage in urban space, create a particular cultural experience, and strengthen the county's identity and image (LCDRC 2022:2-8, 14-15, 19). Place branding in Qingtian involves 'image orchestration' to influence perceptions and enhance the county's reputation. By promoting its positive narratives of diaspora heritage, the county aims to differentiate itself from other regions, attracting tourism and foreign investment.

4.1 Characteristic Township Development

The characteristic township initiative (特色小镇) is an idea to provide a new platform integrating industries, residences, tourism, and culture for small- and medium-sized townships.

Small-to-medium-sized towns became more prioritized for China's urban development and modernization. Characteristics are the chosen qualities with the potential to develop into a leading economic sector. Policy efforts promote regional development, economic diversification, and sustainable urbanization (Y. Wu et al. 2017:23).

The NUP's agenda criticizes urban-rural architecture and spatial design for lacking authenticity and not adapting to the local environment and culture. Therefore, localized urban planning for Lishui stresses a characteristic identity and its maintenance (The State Council of the PRC 2014 n.p.; LCDRC 2022:2-8). The modernization of the country, in which Westernisation and globalization are reflected as the ideal model of a developed entity, is justified by the attempt to preserve the heritage of the diasporic legacy. The city and county authorities describe this development conception as considerable and conscious of local traditions and characteristics. Capitalization of the diasporic values is encapsulated with the idea of an "Overseas Chinese Hometown city brand," the concept of designing an ideal image of the county's future. In particular, Qingtian's characteristic township development concept was chosen to use its migration legacy and promote it as an international trade and tourism center. The plan aspires:

"...to build the most beautiful county city with European-style charm and promote the development of the city brand as a homeland for overseas Chinese."

建设欧陆风情最美县城，推动侨乡城市品牌建设 (LCDRC 2022:3, 14-15).

While Overseas Hometown is one of the identity markers of Qingtian, the county government also uses other features to construct the image of the place brand. The migration legacy celebrates the heroic past of the early generation of migrants and their remittances and donations; now, it is maintained by the diaspora organizations and overseas talents who are returning (163.com n.d. n.p.; China News 2021 n.p.). Another subject of local identity is carved stone, sold by Qingtian merchants all over Europe. The museum, dedicated to carved stone, is located at the center of the county's urban perimeter and was established in 2010 (China News 2015 n.p.). In 2015, China News highlighted the legacy of carved stone and the cultural markers of Qingtian. As part of this recognition, Shangkou Town (山口镇), located within the county, was listed among the towns to be promoted as characteristic towns in Zhejiang Province." Another characteristic is "rice-fish symbiosis" (稻鱼共生)² which became a global agricultural

² Fish provides fertiliser to rice, regulates micro-climatic conditions, softens the soil, disturbs the water, and eats larvae and weeds in the flooded fields; rice provides shade and food for fish (Lansing and Kremer 2011)

heritage (Lishui Government 2023 n.p.;L. Government 2022 n.p.). In 2021, the rice-fish culture was chosen as one of the innovative practices of rural revitalization in Zhejiang Province (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2022). However, this traditional agricultural practice is not unique to the region or only to China. It is practiced in many cultures worldwide (Lansing and Kremer 2011:19841– 19842).

Based on the data available, the migrant's hometown legacy, carved stone craftsmanship, and agricultural innovation are shown as the set of characteristic labels that create Qingtian's unique and competitive identity. Nevertheless, the migration legacy is the most marketed identity layer because of the opportunity and market it provides. Place marketing encompasses identifying, anticipating, and satisfying the needs and desires of target markets. Within a market-based approach, marketing aims to develop and offer products and services that meet the market demand. The Characteristic Development initiative for Overseas Hometowns depicts particular locality qualities that correspond to the market's need or have a chance to develop one. Ideally, a successful place marketing campaign would increase the number of incoming tourists and the potential urban residents or its Overseas diaspora living abroad. Therefore, improving the infrastructure is an important precondition to accommodate anticipated mobility flow. To fill this gap, regional integration of road construction, in the form of the One Belt Three Zones initiative, aims to interconnect counties in Zhejiang with highways.

4.2 Trade and Tourism: Narrating a Story of Success and Beauty

One project of the Lishui plan employs the existing Overseas Chinese economy as a business model concept. The "Qingtian Global Trade and Business Hub" (青田环球商贸聚集中心) with investment is the sole project that incorporates the Overseas Chinese economy and is executed under the auspices of the "Qingtian Overseas Chinese Experimental District Center" (青田县华侨试验区中心). The project started earlier but is ongoing and was projected to be completed in 2023. The shopping mall will be an all-in-one urban complex with imported trade, shopping, tourism, office space, and leisure activities. (Qingtian Government 2023a)

In the context of Qingtian, place promotion has been used to attract domestic tourists, international Overseas Chinese, and investors, communicating its offerings and advantages. This involves promoting local diaspora culture to the outside as part of both historical heritage and present times. Projects such as ICC and the "Qingtian Global Trade and Business Hub" are narrated to provide domestic tourists with an international shopping experience and space for development.

The county is also promoted as a tourist destination for the international diaspora living abroad, aiming to motivate Overseas Chinese to visit their hometown as a root tourism activity (China News 2023 n.p.). At the same time, the local government has been implementing place branding strategies and making use of natural resources to attract domestic tourists (Bofulin 2021:11). The prefecture city government of Lishui invested significantly in building a tourist resort in Beishan Town (北山镇). The development of Qianxia Lake (千峡湖) is described with the concept of overseas Chinese culture, along with other trends of eco-tourism and European style. In the Lishui Plan, Qianxia Lake may seem insignificant compared to others, but the description mentions migrant heritage being used as a storytelling concept for development.

"...relying on the unique mountain and water resources and profound cultural heritage, following the development concept of "nature, ecology, humanities, leisure, and fashion," with the connotation of Overseas Chinese culture and European style..."

...依托独特的山水资源和深厚的文化底蕴，按照“自然、生态、人文、休闲、时尚”的开发理念，以侨乡文化和欧陆风情为内涵... (LCDRC 2022:35).

During the implementation of the Lishui Plan for the 2020-2024 period, the plan placed a strong emphasis on the promotion of Overseas Chinese culture, which was to be interpreted and integrated with elements of Western culture and modernity.

The reinvention and reconstruction of diasporic heritage in Qingtian County exemplify a strategic approach to place branding and urban development. Qingtian leverages its cultural legacy to foster growth and create a distinctive identity through infrastructure projects, economic initiatives, and tourism development. These efforts not only benefit the local economy but also strengthen the bond between the Overseas Hometown and its diaspora, ensuring a sustainable and inclusive future for the region. The Qingtian Global Trade and Business Hub and the Qianxia Lake Ecological Tourism Resort aim to attract foreign investment and tourism while creating new business opportunities and enhancing the region's economic sustainability. Key projects demonstrate how local governments leverage the financial and cultural capital of the diaspora to drive economic development. The Lishui Plan's focus on building highways and improving transportation links is essential for integrating rural areas with urban centers, facilitating trade, and improving access to services. However, the essence of diasporic internationalism and modernity are unnatural and problematic due to its aggressive and artificial Westernisation, which replaces traditional, local authenticity (Liu 2022:

212, 209-227). Diasporic internationalism harms other aspects of culture and heritage that are not categorized, yet possess great value for community and individuals.

4.3 Ancestors Hinder Urban Development

Cooperation between cities, counties, and small townships could increase the general competitiveness, population capacity, and land use efficiency by building roads between (LCDRC 2022:4,8,11,49). The communication and construction projects are planned and realized under the "One Belt, Three Zones" initiative (一带三区, hereafter BTZ) (LCDRC 2022:4). A significant amount of funds has been allocated: the National Highway 330 Qingtian Wenxi to Chuanliao Section Reconstruction Project, with an investment of 88.50 million RMB, aims to build 31.5 km of high-speed road, being the highest total investment for Qingtian County. Its purpose is to connect Qingtian with Wencheng and Leqing.

The construction work is divided into smaller parts between the counties, with each county having limited responsibilities and budget to achieve a communication net. Particularly in Lishui, Qingtian County is presented as the south wing of the belt. Meanwhile, Qingtian and Jinyun plan to integrate into Jinyi's new district and Wenzhou (LCDRC 2022:2,11). There are a few challenges in the realization of this plan. The land designed for construction works is occupied. Therefore, the "National Highway 330 Qingtian Wenxi to Chuanliao Section Reconstruction Project" causes "the demolition of more than 100 acres of land and relocation of more than 200 graves and 20 houses" (Qingtian Government 2023b n.p.). The authorities have shared a notice with a detailed construction plan for the relocation and resettlement area of Tanxia village. The land collection and relocation of graves and compensation for land clearing have been completed. The official grave relocation procedure follows a standard protocol of publishing a "Notice of Grave Relocation" (迁坟启事 or 迁坟通知) in the local press (Mullaney 2019 n.p.). There are three other notices demanding grave relocation.

1. the renovation of the area, graves from the Shiguo Shang and Xia old villages (石郭上、下村旧村) (Qingtian County Broadcasting and Television Station Official Account 2024n.p.).
2. To accommodate the construction needs of the industrial platform project, graves are to be relocated from Dongyuan Village (东源镇东源村) (Qingtian County Dongyuan Town People's Government 2024 n.p.).

3. To make space for constructing a sports center in 2011 (Qingtian County Youzhu New District Management Committee 2011 n.p.).

Accordingly, residents must comply within a short period and should move the graves to another cemetery or may choose to make their arrangements. The tomb will be considered unclaimed if relocation is not completed by the deadline. While improved infrastructure facilitates the movement of people, goods, and services, thereby enhancing residents' overall quality of life, such construction projects may also have ethical issues and contradict the cultural values of ancestry. The legacies of ancestors, many of whom traveled away from home and later returned as loyal contributors to their hometown's prosperity, have now become obstacles to urban development after their passing. Notably, graves hold significant importance for people, serving as a source of place attachments and adding value to familial farmland. Considering that villages and Overseas Hometowns are inhabited mainly by the elderly and children, as well as the high costs and tight deadlines involved in relocation, compliance with development orders is likely challenging for many families.

5. Conclusion

The conceptualization of heritage in urban space-making in the homelands of the Chinese diaspora is evolving along with the urban and tourism development processes. By examining Qingtian economic and urban development narratives, this research analyses urban policies through the lens of place branding. The concept of an Overseas Hometown, as a defining characteristic of these native places of international migrants, has long impacted their sustenance, development, and economic climate (Yow 2007; X. Zhang 2007). The migration legacy has been adopted by diaspora policies to create a place of attachment (Overseas Chinese Barabantseva 2005). Later, migration legacies were integrated into urban planning to create diasporic urban spaces, or, as Liu describes, a process of diasporic place-making (J. Liu 2022). The strategic use of diaspora heritage has significant socio-economic implications, embodying transnationalism, internationalism, and modernity while maintaining a strong connection between diaspora and China. Place branding is one perspective to examine China's strategy to leverage its diaspora for domestic development. Bofulin argues that diaspora policies are not simply passively implemented by local authorities in the county but also undergo a process of experimentation and innovation (Bofulin 2022b). Local and regional governments compete with other local and international markets by shaping how potential consumers perceive their

place (Evan Cleave and Gilliland 2016; Pasquinelli 2013). Thus, place branding theory can help explain how diasporic legacies are implemented in China's urban policies. The Lishui Plan emphasizes comprehensive development and implements characteristic township or thematic branding for specific places (LCDRC 2022; LCDRC 2023).

Diasporic values, or more accurately, labels and features, are strategically integrated into various policies related to urban place branding. Diasporic culture once referred to the international sojourner lifestyle, involving annual visits to the hometown, sending donations, and maintaining cultural identity and a sense of belonging. However, these values are now changing. The reinvention and reconstruction of collective identities are processed under the need to adapt to a modernized and globalized competition-oriented economy, in which local characteristics act as authentic features. However, these authentic features are reconstructed as Western, international, modern, and flexible. In essence, the ideal of Overseas Hometown development is closely tied to young international descendants of Chinese migrants returning to China. These returning overseas Chinese are encouraged to learn from their host countries, remain competitive, represent the state, capitalize on their cultural heritage, and ideally return to their ancestral homeland to contribute to the nation-building process. The small county is given an identical goal to grow and develop for its competitiveness.

More importantly, this study highlights the aspirations of a small township striving to blend urban sophistication with rural resources. The concept of an Overseas Hometown envisions a place that offers modern lifestyles, products, services, infrastructure, and communication networks, all within a natural park. This creates a garden city characterized by unique industries and a collective identity sustained by loyal residents.

The ongoing state-led internationalization of the county, which involves the construction and materialization of diasporic values, serves as a rationale for Westernisation within a broader process of modernization, striving towards an ideal urbanized, civilized, and capitalized society.

Bibliography

163.com. “从贫困县到金融十强县，侨乡青田是如何炼成的？-网易公开课” cong pinkun xian dao jinrong shi qiang xian, qiaoxiang Qingtian shi ruhe liancheng de? -wangyi gongkai ke [From poverty-stricken counties to top 10 financial counties, how did Qingtian, an overseas Chinese hometown, become what it is? -Wangyi Open Course]. Available at

<https://open.163.com/newview/movie/free?pid=LH2RM5BT1&mid=CH2RM5BTR>

(accessed on 16 August, 2024).

Barabantseva, Elena (2005). “Trans-nationalising chineseness: Overseas Chinese policies of the PRC’s central government”. *Asien* 96.July, pp. 7–28.

— (2011). “Transnationalising Chineseness ‘Overseas Chinese work’ in the reform period”. In: *Overseas Chinese, Ethnic Minorities and Nationalism: De-Centering China*. Routledge, pp. 1–202.

Benton, Gregor and Edmund Terence Gomez (2014). “Belonging to the nation: generational change, identity and the Chinese diaspora”. *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 37.7, pp. 1157–1171.

Bofulin, Martina (2016). *Daleč doma : migracije iz Ljudske republike Kitajske v Slovenijo* [Home away from home: migration from PR China to Slovenia], (Series Migration, 25). Ljubljana: ZRC SAZU Publishing House, 2016. 242 p.— (2021). “Imported Commodity City: A New Model for the Development of China’s Emigration Hometowns?” *Anthropological Notebooks* 27.2, pp. 1–20.

— (May 2022a). “Heritagization of Chinese Migration: From Binaries to Connections”. *Asian Studies* 10, pp. 385–396.

— (2022b). “Qiaoxiang 2.0: The People’s Republic of China and Diaspora Governance at the Local Level”. *China Perspectives* 131, pp. 7–15.

Boisen, Martin et al. (2018). “Reframing place promotion, place marketing, and place branding - moving beyond conceptual confusion”. *Cities* 80. *City Marketing and Branding as Urban Policy*, pp. 4–11.

Ceccagno, Antonella (Dec. 2012). “The Hidden Crisis: The Prato Industrial District and the Once Thriving Chinese Garment Industry”. *Revue européenne des migrations internationales* [European Review of International Migrations] 28, pp. 43–65.

Chan, Kam Wing (2007). “Misconceptions and Complexities in the Study of China’s Cities: Definitions, Statistics, and Implications”. *Eurasian Geography and Economics* 48.4, pp. 383–412.

— (2021). “What the 2020 Chinese census tells us about progress in hukou reform”. *China Brief* 21.15, pp. 11–17.

Chen, Chuanbo and C. Cindy Fan (2016). “China’s Hukou Puzzle: Why Don’t Rural Migrants Want Urban Hukou?” *China Review* 16.3, pp. 9–39.

Chen, Murong 陈慕榕, ed. (1990). *青田县志, *Qingtianxianzhi** [Qingtian County Gazetteer]. Hangzhou: Zhejiang People’s Publishing House, pp. 122, 156–159, 172–173, 651.

China News (2015). “探访浙江青田“石雕小镇”：石头雕镂的大千世界” *Shentang Zhejiang Qingtian Shidiao xiaozhen shitou diaolou de daqian shijie* [Visit Zhejiang

Qingtian “stone carving town”: stone carving of the great world]. Available at <<https://www.chinanews.com/df/2015/08-04/7447568.shtml>> (accessed on 18 August, 2024).

— (2021). “海外华裔青年让中外文明交流年轻化、多样化” haiwai huayi qingnian rang zhongwai wenming jiaoliu nianqinghua, duoyanghua [Overseas Chinese Youth Make Sino-Foreign Cultural Exchanges Younger and More Diverse]. Available at <<https://www.gqb.gov.cn/news/2021/1103/52397.shtml>> (accessed on 16 August, 2024).

— (2023). “新生代华侨华人相约侨乡青田“寻根之旅”品味家乡风情” xinshengdai huaqiao huaren xianyue Qiaoxiang Qingtian “xugeng zhi you” pinwei jiaxiang fengqing [The new generation of overseas Chinese meet in the hometown of Qingtian ‘Roots Tour’ taste of home style]. Available at <<https://www.chinanews.com.cn/hr/2023/07-13/10042140.shtml>> (accessed on 18 August, 2024).

— (2023b). “青田，这座县城为何处处显‘洋气’” Qingtian, zhezuo xiancheng weihe ruhe chuchu xian yanqi? [Qingtian, why does this county town show ‘foreign style’ everywhere?] Available at <<https://www.chinanews.com.cn/hr/2023/11-21/10115597.shtml>> (accessed on 18 August, 2024).

Chu, Yin-wah (2020). “China’s new urbanization plan: Progress and structural constraints”. *Cities* 103, p. 102736.

Committee, Qingtian County Gazetteer Compilation (2013). “青田县志 1988-2007” Qingtian xian zhi 1988-2007 [Qingtian County Gazetteer, 1988-2007]. Zhejiang People’s Publishing House, pp. 1–1124.

CEIC Data. Population: Zhejiang: Lishui: Qingtian. n.d. Available at <<https://www.ceicdata.com/en/china/population-county-level-region/population-zhejiang-lishui-qingtian>> (accessed on 20 December, 2023).

Cleave, Evan and Arku, Godwin and Sadler, Richard and Gilliland, Jason (2016). “The role of place branding in local and regional economic development: bridging the gap between policy and practicality”. **Regional Studies, Regional Science** 3.1, pp. 207–228.

Fernández Cavia, José (2011). “Ciudades, regiones y países como marcas: luces y sombras del place branding”. *Manual de comunicación turística: de la formación a la persuasión, de la promoción a la emoción.*-(Documenta; 23), pp. 103–113.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2022). Rice-fish Culture, Qingtian County, China. Available at <<https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/40e90719-4775-4228-afaa-e1e6730df7e6/content/giahs-2022/rice-fishculture.html>> (accessed on 16 August, 2024).

Goodkind, Daniel (2019). “The Chinese diaspora: historical legacies and contemporary trends”. US Department of Commerce, Economics and Statistics Administration, US Census Bureau, pp. 1–45.

Griffiths, Martin and Schiavone, Michael (2016). “China’s New Urbanisation Plan 2014–20”. *China Report* 52.2, pp. 73–91.

Hu, Weijie (2023). “Why did Chongqing’s recent hukou reform fail? A Chinese migrant workers’ perspective”. *Urban Geography* 44.8, pp. 1833–1842.

Kalandides, Ares (2012). “Place branding and place identity. An integrated approach”. *Tafer Journal* 43.1-12, p. 5.

Jemec, Sebastjan (2023). “Sweet Return and Bitter Memories: Rethinking Coffee Culture and Overseas Return Migration from Europe to Rural Fujian, China”. *Journal of Chinese Overseas* 19.1, pp. 57–88.

Lan, Tu and Zhu, Shengjun (2014). “Chinese apparel value chains in Europe: Lowend fast fashion, regionalization, and transnational entrepreneurship in Prato, Italy”. *Eurasian Geography and Economics* 55, pp. 156–174.

Lansing, John Stephen and James N. Kremer (2011). “Rice, fish, and the planet”. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 108.50, pp. 19841–19842.

Latham, Kevin and Bin Wu (2013). *Chinese Immigration into the EU: New Trends, Dynamics and Implications*. London: Europe China Research and Advice Network, pp. 1–65.

LCDRC, Lishui City Development and Reform Commission (2022) 丽水市新型城镇化发展“十四五”规划 Lishui shi xinxing chengzhenghua fazhan 'shisiwu' guihua [Lishui City New Urbanization Development '14th Five-Year Plan']. LCDRC, pp. 1–70.

— (2023). 丽水市新型城镇化发展‘十四五’规划’政策解读, Lishui shi xinxing chengzhenghua fazhan 'shisi wu' guihua' zhengce jiedu [Interpretation of the ”14th Five-Year Plan” for the New Urbanization Development of Lishui City]. Available at <https://www.lishui.gov.cn/art/2023/1/6/art_1229286760_2454209.html> (accessed on 20 December 2023).

Li, Wangming 李王鸣, Zhou, Wen 周雯 and Ji, Gaofeng 季高峰 (2011). “中国区域性特色城市化研究: 以青田县城市化特征为例, Zhongguo quyuxing tese chengshihua yanjiu: yi Qingtianxian chengshihua tezheng weili [Urbanisation with Regional Characteristics in China: The Case of Qingtian County’s Urbanisation Characteristics]”. *城市发展研究* [Urban Development Research] 18.7, pp. 32–37.

Lishui Government (2022). 聚焦农业文化遗产 | 青田“稻鱼共生系统”的传承和保护, jujiao nongye wenhua yichan Qingtian“daoyu gongsheng xitong”de chuancheng he baohu [Focus on Agricultural Cultural Heritage|The Inheritance and Conservation of Qingtian’s Rice-Fish Symbiosis System]. Available at <https://www.lishui.gov.cn/art/2022/7/20/art_1229218389_57336639.html> (accessed on 20 December, 2023).

— (2023). “500 余名华裔新生代在青田开启寻根之旅” 500 yu ming huayi xinshengdai zai Qingtian kaiqi xungen zhi lv [More than 500 Chinese New Generation started the journey to find their roots in Qingtian.] Available at <https://www.lishui.gov.cn/art/2023/7/13/art_1229218391_57348187.html> (accessed on 18 August, 2024).

Liu, Hong and Els van Dongen (2016). “China’s Diaspora Policies as a New Mode of Transnational Governance”. *Journal of Contemporary China* 25.102, pp. 805–821.

Liu, Jiaqi (2022). “Diasporic placemaking: the internationalisation of a migrant hometown in post-socialist China”. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 48.1, pp. 209–227.

Yujing Liu and Hu, Renchuan and Shen, Songsong and Zhang, Zheng and Zhang, Jing and Song, Xiaoling and Qiang, Sheng (2021). “Plant diversity in herbal tea and its traditional knowledge in Qingtian County, Zhejiang Province, China”. *Plant diversity* 42.6, pp. 464–472.

Masdeu, Irene (July 2019). “Migrants’ Descendants and New Mobilities between China and Spain”. *International Migration* 58.

Mobrand, Erik (2015). “Legitimising and Contesting Exclusion: Discussions about Shiminhua in Urban China”. *China: An International Journal* 13.2, pp. 108–122.

Mullaney, Thomas S (2019). “No room for the dead: on grave relocation in contemporary China”. *The Chinese Deathscape: Grave Reform in Modern China*. Available at <<https://chinesedeathscape.org/>> (accessed on 16 August 2024).

Ottati, Gabi Dei and Cologna, Daniele Brigadoi (2015). “The Chinese in Prato and the Current Outlook on the Chinese-Italian Experience”. In: *Chinese Migration to Europe: Prato, Italy, and Beyond*. Ed. by Loretta Baldassar et al. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, pp. 29–48.

Pasquinelli, Cecilia (2013). “Competition, cooperation and co-opetition: unfolding the process of inter-territorial branding”. *Urban Research & Practice* 6.1, pp. 1–18.

Qingtian County Broadcasting and Television Station Official Account (2024). “青田县瓯南街道石郭上、下村旧村改造项目坟墓迁移公告, Qingtian County Ounan Street

Shiguo Shang and Xia Villages Old Village Renovation Project Tomb Relocation Notice. Available at <<https://new.qq.com/rain/a/20240314A0604F00>> (accessed on 16 August 2024).

Qingtian County Dongyuan Town People’s Government (2024). “青田县东源镇东源村门前山项目坟墓迁移公告”, Qingtian xian Dongyuan zhen Dongyuan cun Menqianshan xiangmu fenmu qianyi gonggao [Notice of Grave Relocation for the Menqianshan Project in Dongyuan Village, Dongyuan Town, Qingtian County] Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2024/3/20/art_1229429378_5279355.html> (accessed on 16 March 2024).

Qingtian County Youzhu New District Management Committee (2011). “迁坟通告”, Qianfen tonggao [Relocation of Graves Notice]. Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2011/2/18/art_1229390741_100929.html> (accessed on 16 August 2024).

Qingtian Government (2017). “青田实施浙江省相关人才政策 18 岁以上华侨可落户”, Qingtian shishi Zhejiangsheng xiangguan rencai zhengce 18 sui yishang Huaqiao ke luohu [Qingtian implements Zhejiang Province’s talent policy, overseas Chinese aged 18 and over can settle down]. accessed on September 26, 2023. URL: <https://www.gqb.gov.cn/news/2017/0317/42004.shtml>.

— (2020). “接轨千峡湖以“五个一”为抓手激活小溪旅游开发”, jiegui Qianxia Hu yi ”wu ge yi” wei zhua shou jihuo Xiaoxi lüyou kaifa [Integrate with Qianxia Lake, Activate Xiaoxi Tourism Development with ”Five Ones” as the Focus]. Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2020/9/9/art_1229385871_108043.html> (accessed on 16 August, 2024).

— (2021). “华侨之乡—青田”, Huaqiao zhi xiang—Qingtian [The Hometown of Overseas Chinese—Qingtian]. Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2021/9/6/art_1229366331_485055.html> (accessed on 16 August, 2024).

— (2022). “人口老龄化对青田经济发展的影响研究”, renkou laolinghua dui Qingtian jingji fazhan de yingxiang yangjiu [Impact of Population Aging on the Economic Development of Qingtian: A Study]. Available at <http://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2022/10/9/art_1229392770_5005431.html> (accessed on 20 December, 2023).

— (2022b). “关于青田县第十七届人民代表大会第一次会议第 140 号提案的答复”, guanyu Qingtian xian di shiqi jie renmin daibiao dahui diyi ci huiyi di 140 hao ti’an de dafu [Response to Proposal No. 140 of the First Session of the 17th People’s Congress of Qingtian County]. Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2022/11/30/art_1229437161_5031242.html> (accessed on 16 August 2024).

— (2023a). “青田县住房和城乡建设局关于青田环球购物中心工程项目（青城公寓）现售许可的公示”, Qingtian xian zhufang he chengxiang jianshe ju guanyu Qingtian Huanqiu Gouwu Zhongxin gongcheng xiangmu (Qingcheng gongyu) xian shou xuke de gongshi. [Public Notice from the Qingtian County Housing and Urban-Rural Development Bureau Regarding the Pre-sale Permit for the Qingtian Global Shopping Center Construction Project (Qingcheng Apartments)] Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2024/1/31/art_1229428907_5259566.html> (accessed on 16 August 2024).

— (2023b). “青田县鹤城街道坦下村搬迁安置区块修建性详细规划》批后公布”, Qingtian xian hecheng jiedao Tanxia cun banqian anzhi kuaixiu jianxing xiangxi guihua pihou gongbu [Qingtian County Hecheng Street Tanxia Village relocation resettlement block

construction detailed planning” after the approval published]. Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2023/7/7/art_1229444058_5138736.html>

(accessed on 20 May 2024).

— (2024). “行政区划”, xinzheng quhua [Implement zoning plan]. Available at <https://www.qingtian.gov.cn/art/2024/3/26/art_1229723270_501268.html> (accessed on 16 August 2024).

Rabe, Wiebke (2022). “China’s Provinces Go Global: Internationalization Under Guided Autonomy”. Routledge, pp. 1–200.

de San Eugenio-Vela, Jordi and Ginesta, Xavier and Compte-Pujol, Marc and Frigola-Reig, Joan and Fernández-Rovira, Cristina (2023). “The Process of Implementing a Place Brand Based on a Multilevel Approach: The Case of the Municipality of Masquefa” *Sustainability* 15, no. 22:15788, pp.1-17

de San Eugenio Vela, Jordi (2013). Place branding: A conceptual and theoretical framework. *Boletín de la Asociación de Geógrafos Españoles*, 62, pp. 189-211+467-471.

Tao, Ruyu, Pinyu Chen, and Nobuo Aoki (2024). “The Shaping of “New Gentry” Discourse in the Context of China’s Rural Revitalisation and Heritage Conservation Strategy”. *China Perspectives*, pp. 45–55.

Thünken, Florian (2020). “Rural-to-Urban Transition in Chongqing’s Hinterland: StateLed Urbanisation or Urbanisation From Below?” *Journal of Current Chinese Affairs* 49.3, pp. 312–331.

Thunø, Mette (2018). “China’s New Global Position: Changing Policies towards the Chinese Diaspora in the 21st Century”. In: *China’s Rise and the Chinese Overseas*. Ed. by Bernard and Tan Chee-Beng Wong. Routledge, pp. 184–208.

Wang, Cangbai (2017). “Heritage as theatre: Reconceptualizing heritage-making in urban China”. *China Information* 31.2, pp. 195–215.

— (2020). “Ambivalent Heritage: The Im/Possibility of Museumifying the Overseas Chinese in South China”. *Modern China* 46.6, pp. 559–584.

Wang, Wei et al. (2017). “Development priority zoning in China and its impact on urban growth management strategy”. *Cities* 62, pp. 1–9. ISSN: 0264-2751.

Wu, Yuzhe et al. (2017). “Development of Characteristic Towns in China”. *Habitat International* 77, pp. 21–31.

Xu Hui, 徐辉 (2021). “青田县方山乡华侨留守儿童现状调查”, *Qingtian xian Fangshan xiang huaqiao liu shou er tong xianzhuang diaocha* [A Survey of Overseas Chinese Left-Behind Children in Fangshan Township, Qingtian County]”. *八桂侨刊 Bagui Qiaokan* [Overseas Chinese Journal of Bagui] 4. Wenzhou International Studies University, Zhejiang Wenzhou, pp. 82–93.

Yow, Hoe Cheun (2007). “Detraditionalized and Renewed Qiaoxiang Areas: Case Studies of Panyu and Wenzhou in the Reform Period Since 1978”. In: *Beyond Chinatown: New Chinese Migration and the Global Expansion of China*. Ed. by Mette Thunoe. Copenhagen, Denmark: NIAS –Nordic Institute of Asian Studies, pp. 67–82.

Zhang, Xiuming (2007). “Remittances, Donations and Investments in Qingtian County Since 1978”. In: *Beyond Chinatown: New Chinese Migration and the Global Expansion of China*. Ed. by Mette Thunø. Copenhagen, Denmark: NIAS –Nordic Institute of Asian Studies, pp. 67–82.

Zhejiang Todays (2002). “丽水努力开发” 华侨经济”, Lishui nuli kaifa Huaqiao jingji [Lishui strives to develop ”overseas Chinese economy]”. *Zhejiang Todays* 20, pp. 38– 39.

Zhu, Yujie and Christina Maags (2020). “Institutions and discourse”. In: *Heritage politics in China: The power of the past*. Routledge, pp. 44–64.

Appendix A

Project title	Budget in 100 million RMB	Share of budget	Economic sector
Qingtian Global Trade and Business Hub, 青田环球商贸聚集中心	10	2.70%	trade
Qingtian County Old City Core Area Renovation Project, 青田县老城核心区旧城改造项目	80	21.60%	infrastructure
Qingtian County Xiaoxi Water Conservancy Hub Project, 青田县小溪水利枢纽工程	14.55	3.93%	infrastructure
Qingtian County Pumped Storage Power Station, 青田县抽水蓄能电站	70	18.9	infrastructure
Qingtian Rehabilitation Hospital, 青田康复	2.52	0.68%	healthcare

医院			
Qingtian County Third People's Hospital (Central Hospital), 青田县第三人民医院 (中部医院)	4.4	1.19%	healthcare
Qingtian to Wencheng Expressway (Qingtian Section), 青田至文成高速公路 (青田段)	88.5	23.89%	communication
Leqing to Qingtian Expressway (Qingtian Section), 乐清至青田高速 (青田段)	45	12.15%	communication
National Highway 330 Qingtian Wenxi to Chuanliao Section Reconstruction Project 330 国道青田温溪至船寮段改建工程	45.7	12.33%	communication
Qingtian County Vocational and Technical School Expansion Project, 青田县职业技术学校扩建工程	4.8	1.30%	education
Qingtian County Sanxikou Middle School New Construction Project, 青田县三溪口中学校新建项目	4.8	1.30%	education
Total:	370.27		

Table 1: Investment budget for development projects in Qingtian county. Author's table based on data from LCDRC [2022:50-70](#)

“The Formation of the Western Tradition of the Still Life Genre with the Inclusion of Chinese Porcelain”

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Abstract: The field of contemporary art history has shown a strong interest in exploring the cross-cultural interactions between continents, particularly those involving Europe and Asia. Within this broad scope, there has been a significant focus on examining the cultural exchanges and reciprocal influences between China and Western countries. This research is part of a scholarly effort to offer insights into the artistic representations of Chinese ceramics in early European still-life paintings. Such representations established the tradition of incorporating Chinese commodities, particularly porcelain vessels, and figurines, in European still-life depictions, which later expanded in the 18th century to chinoiserie and the Aesthetic movement, with its enthusiasm for chinaware in the 19th century.

Our primary goal is to provide an analysis of the pioneering artistic portrayals of Chinese commodities that shaped Western perceptions of distant lands, aiming to demonstrate the dynamism inherent in the formation, continuity, and evolution of the Western¹ tradition, which involved Chinese items in still-life works. Upon conducting a comparative analysis, it is evident that a number of depictions of Chinese export objects aim to glorify and mystify Asian goods. Others are inclined to showcase the imperialistic ambitions of the West, as goods can also be regarded as signs of privilege and trophies synonymous with control and power². This dichotomy in representation underscores the intricate interplay between cultural appreciation and geopolitical hegemony within the framework of global trade and intercultural exchange.

Keywords: Chinese porcelain, Chinese figurine, still life, Western tradition, Renaissance art, Dutch baroque, Spanish baroque

¹ For the purpose of the present survey, the term “West” will be defined as “North America and the countries in the western part of Europe,” as per the Cambridge Academic Content Dictionary. This definition is employed considering that the roots of Western art can be traced back to the creative output of ancient Greece and Rome. These foundations were refined and disseminated across the European continent with the advent of Christianity, and by the late 15th century, European artistic styles had begun to make their way to the New World, giving rise to American and Canadian traditions that were closely intertwined with those of Europe.

² Julie Hochstrasser, *Still Life and Trade in the Dutch Golden Age* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2007), 274.

Introduction

In the words of Robert Finlay, a prominent historian, Chinese philosophy, art, architecture, and landscape design left an indelible mark on Europe's aristocracy since their first encounters³. This led to the creation of numerous travel accounts, meticulous descriptions, publications, and illustrations of Chinese philosophy, culture, science, arts and crafts, as well as attempts to decipher the “other” cultural, social, and religious practices and customs of the celestial empire⁴.

Chinese blue and white porcelain, a type of underglaze ceramic decorated with blue pigment, typically cobalt oxide, was initially introduced to Europe during the fourteenth century⁵, causing a sensation particularly being viewed in comparison with the European pottery pieces that lacked a bright palette and durability. As Chinese ceramic vessels were regarded as objects of great rarity and luxury, some that appeared in Europe in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries were often mounted in gilt silver, which served to heighten the perceived preciousness of the porcelains. Richard Hakluyt's second edition of “The Principal Navigations” (1598–1600) calls the chinaware “the best earthen matter in the world.”⁶ The artistic giant of the Northern Renaissance (15-16th centuries), Albrecht Dürer (1471-1528), avidly collected for his professional and personal pleasure, and he was fascinated by the objects of natural rarity and of exotic, non-European origins. Although we do not own the visual evidence in the form of artistic executions, archival documents prove that among his favorable pieces were costly Asian imports, such as Chinese porcelain.⁷ In addition, numerous representations and extant specimens of the European *Kunstkammer* and *Wunderkammer* reveal the presence of Chinese export porcelain among the coveted items of wonder and collection.⁸ Portugal's Santos Palace ornamentation serves as an epitome of the

³ Robert Finlay, “China, the West, and World History in Joseph Needham's ‘Science and Civilisation in China.’” *Journal of World History* 11, no. 2 (2000): 267.

⁴ Anne Gerristen and Stephen McDowall. “Material Culture and the Other: European Encounters with Chinese Porcelain, ca. 1650–1800.” *Journal of World History* 23, no. 1 (2012): 88.

⁵ Marco Polo brought this delicate ware from China or ‘Cathay’ to Europe in the 14th century and called it “porcellana”, See Joseph Downs, “The China Trade and Its Influences.” *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin* 36, no. 4 (1941): 84–95.

⁶ Richard Hakluyt's second edition of “The Principal Navigations” (1598–1600), London, 67.

⁷ Jeffrey Chipps Smith, “The 2010 Josephine Waters Bennett Lecture: Albrecht as Collector.” *Renaissance Quarterly* 64, no. 1 (2011): 27.

⁸ See Frans II Francken (Flemish, 1581–1642), Chamber of Art and Rarity, 1620/1625, oak wood, Kunsthistorisches Museum, Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum Wien, Gemäldegalerie, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.khm.at/objektdb/detail/751/>, includes the Ming porcelain bowl.

grandeur and opulence of the era, featuring a complex fusion of Neoclassical mythological themes and almost 200 rare porcelain plates from the Ming dynasty Chinese export mounted to the ceiling during the 16th and 17th centuries.⁹ Sophie Charlotte, the inaugural Queen consort of Prussia, undertook the commissioning of Charlottenburg Palace in the early 1700s, with an exceptional display of Chinese and Japanese porcelain vessels and figurines within a dedicated Porcelain Room.¹⁰

The integration of Chinese commodities in European visual arts, specifically in paintings, echoed the above-mentioned processes and tendencies and has established a tradition that incorporates chinaware in still-life compositions or paintings featuring still-life arrangements. Chinese porcelain and ceramic figurines have become a prevalent motif in Western still life, manifested through various artistic perspectives and stylistic implementations for assorted purposes. The concept of tradition¹¹ is closely associated with the notions of repetition, rigidity, and immutability on one hand and dynamism and transformation on the other. Therefore, we utilize the notion of tradition to explore the principles of continuity and change within the depictions of chinaware in European still life, which are deeply intertwined with the socio-historical and commercial exchanges between Europe and Asia, as well as the artistic trends of the time.

First European encounters with China and pioneering depictions of Chinese commodities

The field of art history is yet to establish conclusive evidence regarding the pioneering artists who first incorporated Chinese porcelain as a compositional element in their paintings. Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that during the Renaissance (circa 1500-1600) and Early Modern period (circa 1500–1800), the relative inaccessibility of Chinese commodities gave rise to a mythology of Chinese mystery and exoticism, motivating artists to imbue depictions of chinaware with qualities of inestimable integrity, virtue, and divinity which, to some

⁹ Daisy Lion-Goldschmidt, "Les Porcelaines Chinoises Du Palais de Santos." *Arts Asiatiques* 39 (1984): 7.

¹⁰ Clare Le Corbeiller, "German Porcelain of the Eighteenth Century." *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin* 47, no. 4 (1990): 6.

¹¹ John La Farge, "Tradition and Art." *The Irish Monthly* 71, no. 843 (1943): 378.

extent, appears to be a part of the Orientalist¹² discourses of the East. It is important to consider that still life, as a distinct, independent genre, emerged and developed only in the 16th century, and the first fine arts monuments featuring depictions of chinaware were either religious or historical compositions that incorporated still-life elements.

In this regard, the Italian painter of the Renaissance period, Francesco Benaglio (1432–1492), with his “Madonna and Child” (circa the 1460s),¹³ might be considered one of the first to-date European artists who employed the Chinese export bowl as a divine, otherworldly essence of Christian protagonists. The painting depicts the Virgin holding the Christ child on a cushion made of velvet while a blue-and-white bowl filled with fresh figs is placed on the right side of the viewer. The employment of such a vessel by the mother of God signifies the high esteem in which Chinese porcelain was held during that time. Bowls with a similar design were crafted during the preceding Yongle period 永樂 (1403–1425), leading to the possibility that the bowl depicted in the painting was produced earlier during the Yongle era.¹⁴ The British Museum houses one such type of bowl from the Ming dynasty with an identical design and Xuande (宣德, (1425 to 1435) mark.¹⁵

Supposedly, the Renaissance masterpiece “The Madonna and the Book” (circa 1482–1483) by Sandro Botticelli (1445 circa –1510) and Filippino Lippi (1457 circa –1504)¹⁶ demonstrated either a precious Chinese blue-and-white porcelain bowl next to Madonna and Christ or a piece of the first European failed imitations of Chinese ceramics. The cherries in the bowl allude to the blood of Christ, the plums to the sweetness of the love which the Virgin bears towards her child, and the figs to the Resurrection of Christ. Within this

¹² The term “Orientalism,” as expounded by Edward W. Said, is a consequential study that draws strong parallels with the nature of all existing European movements and styles that have been based on the utilization of Oriental subjects and motifs. Said notes that the Orient and the Oriental, whether it be Arab, Islamic, Indian, Chinese, or other, have become repetitious pseudo-incarnations of some great original, such as Christ, Europe, or the West, that they were supposed to have been imitating. The source of these rather narcissistic Western ideas about the Orient changed in time, but their character remained the same. Said also identifies the vision of China and the Chinese people in Western art as being “perfidious.” (See, Edward W. Said, *Orientalism* (New York: Pantheon Books, 1978), 62, 108).

¹³ Francesco Benaglio (Italian painter of the Renaissance period) Veronese, c. 1432–1492, *Madonna and Child*, late 1460s, tempera on panel transferred to canvas, overall: 80.7 x 56.2 cm (31 3/4 x 22 1/8 in.), framed: 106.4 x 81.6 x 5.7 cm (41 7/8 x 32 1/8 x 2 1/4 in.), National Gallery of Art, Washington, Widener Collection 1942.9.44, accessed April, 2024, <https://www.nga.gov/collection/art-object-page.1183.html>.

¹⁴ Jessica Harrison-Hall, *Catalog of late Yuan and Ming ceramics in the British Museum* (London: British Museum, 2001), 201.

¹⁵ Porcelain bowl, Ming dynasty, Yongle (period), 1403–1424, Jingdezhen, China, The British Museum, London, 1952,0513.2, accessed April 24, 2024, https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/A_1952-0513-2.

¹⁶ Sandro Botticelli (1445 circa –1510) and Filippino Lippi (1457 circa –1504), *Madonna col Bambino detta “Madonna del Libro” / Madonna and Child* is known as “The Madonna of the Book”, circa 1482–1483, tempera on wood, 58 × 39,5 cm, Museo Poldi Pezzoli, Milan.

context, it's noteworthy that European powers not only admired but were inclined to uncover the secret of the highly valued Chinese porcelain pieces. The porcelain made at the Medici workshops in Florence was the first to be produced in Europe. Francesco I de Medici established a ceramic workshop in the 1560s with the intention of imitating Chinese blue-and-white porcelain.¹⁷ Nonetheless, technically difficult and expensive to make, the fifty-nine pieces of Medici porcelain lack the ingredients that comprise hard-paste porcelain made by the Chinese.

One of the well-known paintings, with the early European exception of the Chinese ceramic piece as a compositional compound, might be regarded as the “Adoration of the Magi” (circa 1495–1500) by Andrea Mantegna¹⁸ (circa 1431–1506) (fig.1), the court painter of the powerful Gonzaga family. The painting portrays three kings paying homage to the Christ Child, who returns the gesture by making a sign of blessing. While Jesus Christ, his mother, the Virgin Mary, and Mary’s husband, Joseph, are depicted wearing simple garments and haloes, the Magi are dressed in exotic clothing and adorned with exquisite jewels, bringing with them a collection of rare gifts. Among the Magi, Caspar is bearded and bareheaded, presenting the Christ Child with a delicate porcelain cup from China filled with gold coins, seemingly completing the circumference of the East. The Paduan audience would have been enchanted by the gifts of the Magi, their jewels, and textured clothes, providing an insight into the mysterious culture and people of the East. Notably, the porcelain cup would have been a rare oddity when the painting was created, and Mantegna likely had access to Ming porcelains from the collection of his patrons, including the Marquise de Gonzaga of Mantua and Pope Innocent VIII.

¹⁷ Clare Le Corbeiller, “A Medici Porcelain Pilgrim Flask.” *The J. Paul Getty Museum Journal* 16 (1988): 120.

¹⁸ Andrea Mantegna (Italian, about 1431–1506), “Adoration of the Magi,” about 1495–1505, Distemper on linen, 48.6 × 65.6 cm (19 1/8 × 25 13/16 in.), J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles, 85.PA.417, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.getty.edu/art/collection/object/103RHD>.

Figure 1: Andrea Mantegna (Italian, about 1431 - 1506), Adoration of the Magi ¹⁹

Rosamond Mack notes the blue motif of flower stems and leaves on the cup, which recalls flower scrolls on early fifteenth-century Ming blue-and-white, but Mantegna slightly altered the cup's shape and decoration to fit the Magus's grasp.²⁰ Interestingly, the cup occupies the foreground of the painting, at the same time being close to Christ. The detailed particularity of the exquisite non-European gifts acknowledges the way the West economically and culturally benefits through Christian conversion. It represents the spread of Christianity throughout the world and its ability to reach even the most remote areas. If we view the painting within the historical context of Italy's burgeoning consumer culture, the porcelain bowl represents a highly desirable luxury item meant for the Son of God himself. Finally,

¹⁹ Andrea Mantegna (Italian, about 1431 - 1506), Adoration of the Magi, about 1495–1505, Distemper on linen, 48.6 × 65.6 cm (19 1/8 × 25 13/16 in.), J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles, 85.PA. 417, <https://www.getty.edu/art/collection/object/103RHD>

²⁰ Rosamond E. Mack, "Patterned Silks," in *Bazaar to Piazza: Islamic Trade and Italian Art, 1300-1600* (Berkeley: the University of California Press, 2002), 32.

from the artistic prism, it subtly perpetuates the interest of the creator and commissioners towards the Chinese goods, forming a fantasy of Italy's access to the East.²¹

Painted by Giovanni Bellini (circa 1430/1435–1516), and completed by the forerunner of the Venetian school, Titian “Feast of the Gods”²² (1514–1529) (fig. 2) offers a certain decontextualization of Chinese blue-and-white porcelain simultaneously accentuating and trivializing their exalted value. Unlike its predecessors that emphasized the interconnection of the rarity of chinaware with the purity and might of Christian saints, this artwork juxtaposes the classical antiquity interpreted in the feast scene of Greco-Roman gods and goddesses with three large pieces of the fifteenth-century porcelain: one held by a nymph, another by a satyr, and the third filled with fruits and depicted in front of Neptune.

Figure 2: Giovanni Bellini (painter) Venetian²³

²¹ Jane Hwang Degenhardt, “Cracking the Mysteries of ‘China’: China(Ware) in the Early Modern Imagination.” *Studies in Philology* 110, no. 1 (2013): 138.

²² Giovanni Bellini (painter) Venetian, c. 1430/1435–1516, Titian (painter) Venetian, 1488/1490–1576, “Feast of the Gods,” 1514–1529, oil on canvas, 67 x 74 in. (170 x 188 cm), National Gallery of Art, Washington, DC, 1942.9.1, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.nga.gov/collection/art-object-page.1138.html>.

²³ Giovanni Bellini (painter) Venetian, c. 1430/1435 - 1516, Titian (painter) Venetian, 1488/1490 - 1576, *Feast of the Gods*, 1514–29, oil on canvas, 67 x 74 in. (170 x 188 cm), National Gallery of Art, Washington, DC, 1942.9.1, <https://www.nga.gov/collection/art-object-page.1138.html>

John A. Pope stated that the images of the Chinese porcelain render the pieces made in China between 1470 and 1510.²⁴ According to another hypothesis, Mehmed II, the Sultan of the Ottoman Empire, gave those valuable pieces as gifts to Bellini's brother, Gentile, whose visit to Constantinople has been recorded in textual sources. The ornamental system and the formal qualities of Chinese bowls resemble the numerous Chinese blue-and-white pieces in the Topkapi Saray Museum in Istanbul. Mack suggested that large, densely painted palmettes and blossoms framed by scrolls and tendrils correspond to the decoration of the Ming type that was exported to Persia, Syria, and Egypt.²⁵

We can assume that the artist could have also gotten acquainted with the rare Chinese ceramics due to his ties with Duke Alfonso I d'Este of Ferrara²⁶ (1476-1534), who was interested in collecting Chinese porcelains. These porcelains can also be interpreted as important evidence of cross-cultural interchange, because they were made in China, they reached the Sultan's collection in the late 1490s, and, lastly, in 1508 were sent as precious diplomatic gifts to Venice. The fact that these vessels made their way from China to the West underscores the far-reaching and dynamic nature of global trade during this period. J. Degenhardt argues that the significance of porcelain as an Italian collector's item might provide additional insight into the inclusion of those Ming pieces both in Mantegna's and Bellini's paintings, who were contemporaries and knew each other. Isabella d'Este, Duchess of Mantua, who was supposedly the commissioner of Mantegna's painting, was known for her magnificent art collection that contained Chinese porcelain pieces. Degenhardt presumes that Bellini, in his turn, imitated the samples from the identical collection in the above-discussed "The Feast of the Gods."²⁷ Hereby, both Mantegna and Bellini had similar inspirational sources for featuring Chinese ceramics.

It's noteworthy that Vincenzo Campi (circa 1530-1591), the 16th-century Italian painter of the Late Renaissance period, who was best known for his pioneering Flemish style of realist genre paintings, has embodied Chinese porcelain in one of his genre paintings— "Fruit

²⁴ John A. Pope and A. G. Wenley, *China* (Smithsonian Institution War Background Studies Number Twenty), (Washington, D. C.: Smithsonian Inst., 1944), 27.

²⁵ Rosamond E. Mack, "Patterned Silks," in *Bazaar to Piazza*, 40.

²⁶ "The Feast of Gods" was the first in a series of mythologies, or bacchanals, commissioned by Duke Alfonso d'Este to decorate the camerino d'alabastro (alabaster study) of his castle in Ferrara, Jaynie Anderson, "The Provenance of Bellini's Feast of the Gods and a New/Old Interpretation." *Studies in the History of Art* 45 (1993): 264–287, repro. no. 10.

²⁷ Degenhardt, "Cracking the Mysteries of 'China'," 143.

Seller” (1578–1581).”²⁸ This image, widely regarded as a significant precedent for Italian still-life painting, is part of a collection of four paintings.²⁹ Together these paintings possess symbolic significance and may represent the four classical elements. In this interpretation, this particular painting would signify the element of Earth, setting new horizons for the allegorical employment of chinaware in the Western tradition.

Dutch Baroque’s Pronk *stilleven* and Chinaware

The Chinese porcelains arrived in the Netherlands in larger quantities during the early 17th century as war booty from Portuguese vessels, known as *Kraak*.³⁰ The Dutch East India Company (VOC) revolutionized and transformed the Asian trade networks, becoming the major supplier of chinaware to all of Europe.³¹

Chinese export porcelain was an essential motif in colorful *ontbijtjes* (“breakfast pieces”), *banketjes* (“banquet pieces”), and more particularly in *Pronk stilleven*³²—a type of still-life painting popular in Dutch art from the mid-to-late 17th century, featuring elaborate displays of costly foodstuffs and luxury household objects. The Chinese porcelain was not presented in isolation but juxtaposed with domestic goods and edibles, Oriental tapestry, and Venetian glass as the epitome of economic power and taste of the patron. Most of the canvases produced during the Age of Enlightenment (circa 1685 – 1815) were commissioned by the affluent mercantile class as a reflection of their identity, leisure activities, familiarity with the arts, and depth of knowledge. In terms of aesthetics, artists exhibited a keen interest in incorporating blue and white hues, shimmering reflections of light on the smooth surfaces of Chinese vessels into their masterpieces, often utilizing that palette in combination with exotic

²⁸ Vincenzo Campi, “Fruit Seller,” 1578–1581, oil on canvas, 143 x 213 cm, Brera Pinacoteca, 397, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://pinacotecabrera.org/en/collezione-online/opere/fruit-seller/>.

²⁹ The painting is part of a series of four genre paintings originally housed in the guest quarters of the Hieronymite monastery of San Sigismondo in Cremona, Italy. Presently, these four canvases are situated in the Pinacoteca di Brera, Milan. In addition to the “Fruit Seller,” the remaining three paintings, namely “Fishmongers” (c. 1580, oil on canvas Pinacoteca di Brera, Milan), “Kitchen” (c. 1580s, oil on canvas Pinacoteca di Brera, Milan), and “Chicken Vendors” (1580s, oil on canvas Pinacoteca di Brera, Milan), share similar thematic content. These works have been the subject of diverse interpretations, including traditional allegories of the four elements or references to the seasons of the year.

³⁰ The Dutch name *Kraak* or *kraakporselein* was employed to describe the Chinese imports.

³¹ Tonio Andrade, “The Dutch East India Company in Global History: A Historiographical Reconnaissance,” in *The Dutch and English East India Companies: Diplomacy, Trade and Violence in Early Modern Asia*, ed. Adam Clulow and Tristan Mostert (Amsterdam University Press, 2018), 240.

³² P. J. J. Van Thiel, “Een Stilleven Door Pieter Claesz.” *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum* 23, no. 2 (1975), 119–121.

patterns, glossy surfaces, reflective textures of other objects to create their signature styles. It is worth noting that, contrary to the early depictions of chinaware in Renaissance art pieces, the chinaware featured in Dutch Baroque still life works is easily identifiable due to the meticulous attention to detail and the use of darkened backdrops that made the porcelain pieces stand out to the viewer.

Willem Kalf (1619–1693), the remarkable Dutch artist who left an impressive artistic heritage with the highlighted depictions of Chinese blue-and-white porcelain³³ (fig. 3), used those Asian items to appeal to the elite burgher audience who had accumulated wealth from the mercantile prosperity of the Dutch Republic. Kalf was not only influential in the process of development of the Western still life genre with his innovative manner, composition, and combinations of props but can also be credited, more importantly for our research, as one of the founders of the Western tradition of still life with Chinese ceramics as major compositional elements.³⁴ The structure of Kalf's still lifes is characterized by precise lighting direction meticulously planned down to the smallest detail, and the use of an imperceptible light source, which selectively illuminates only the most intensely colored objects. Among the illuminated compositional elements are the figurative and floral motifs present in Chinese porcelain.³⁵

³³ Willem Kalf (Dutch, 1619–1693), "Still Life with a Chinese Porcelain Jar," 1669, oil on canvas, 30-3/4 x 26 in. (canvas), 42-5/8 x 37-5/8 x 4-1/4 in. (framed), Indianapolis Museum of Art, 45.9, accessed April 24, 2024, <http://collection.imamuseum.org/artwork/57562/index.html>.

³⁴ In the still life of one of his assistants or followers (After Willem Kalf, "Still Life with Nautilus Cup," 1665/1670, oil on canvas, overall: 68.2 x 58 cm (26 7/8 x 22 13/16 in.), framed: 90.8 x 80 x 9.5 cm (35 3/4 x 31 1/2 x 3 3/4 in.), National Gallery of Art, Washington, 1974.109.1) the blue-and-white Wan-Li porcelain bowl with lid is decorated with colored figures representing the eight immortals of Taoist belief. See, National Gallery of Art, Washington, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.nga.gov/collection/art-object-page.54976>.

³⁵ Lucius Grisebach, Willem Kalf, 1619-1693, (Berlin: Gebr Mann Verlag, 1974), 278–79.

Figure 3: Willem Kalf (Dutch, 1619–1693), Still Life with a Chinese Porcelain Jar³⁶

One of his followers, Juriaen van Streeck (1632–1687), whose oeuvre is specified with the indications of the transience of life through the arrangements of overseas objects, brought

³⁶ Willem Kalf (Dutch, 1619–1693), Still Life with a Chinese Porcelain Jar, 1669, oil on canvas, 30-3/4 x 26 in. (canvas); approximately 42-5/8 x 37-5/8 x 4-1/4 in. (framed), Indianapolis Museum of Art at Newfields, Gift of Mrs. James W. Fesler in memory of Daniel W. and Elizabeth C. Marmon, 45.9. <https://collections.discovernewfields.org/artwork/57562>

new juxtapositions of Chinese precious porcelain pieces with the human figures, more precisely with the African servants³⁷ (fig. 4). However, the piece presents various interpretive possibilities. Within the framework of the Dutch still-life genre conveying cultural insensitivity in the mid to late 1600s, the porcelain in relation to the Moor figure may have been intended to underscore the multicultural nature of Amsterdam. On the other hand, the enslaved figure could have been interpreted as a symbol of affluence, akin to the lobster or jewels. The presentation of the Moor as if on a silver platter in this piece signifies the colonial expansion of the northern Netherlands, globalism, consumerism, and the negative aspects of Western upper classes' attitudes towards the “otherness” of the East.

Figure 4: Juriaen van Streeck, Prunkstillleben mit Diener³⁸

³⁷ Juriaen van Streeck, “Still Life with Moor and Porcelain Vessels,” ca. 1670–1680, Sammlung Shack/Bayerische Staatsgemäldesammlungen, 6599, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.sammlung.pinakothek.de/en/artwork/APL8q0NGN2/juriaen-van-streeck/prunkstillleben-mit-diener>

³⁸ Juriaen van Streeck, Prunkstillleben mit Diener, um 1670/80, Bayerische Staatsgemäldesammlungen - Alte Pinakothek München, URL: <https://sammlung.pinakothek.de/en/artwork/APL8q0NGN2>

Rembrandt van Rein (1606–1669), the innovative and prolific face of the Dutch Golden Age, has authored one of the earliest depictions of a Western art connoisseur and collector,³⁹ surrounded by Chinese artifacts. Abraham Francen (1612 – after 1678) was an Amsterdam apothecary and passionate art collector. This detailed print reflects Rembrandt’s affection for his dear friend, who lived in the modest neighborhood where Rembrandt moved in 1658 after his insolvency. His work might, therefore, be seen as a token of friendship rather than a commissioned portrait. Rembrandt included the still-life arrangement as attributes to uncover the sitter’s character; the figure is surrounded by his cultural valuables, for instance, a painted triptych and a covered Chinese ginger jar. The large album on the table would have held prints and drawings, such as the sheet he examines here with rapt attention. The skull may allude to his profession or function as a traditional *vanitas* symbol of the transience of the material world.

The small-scale Chinese statute next to the skull is defined in the catalog of the Fine Arts Museum of San Francisco as a “figurine of Confucius.”⁴⁰ More resembling the Ming dynasty figurine of a court official according to the shape of the headgear and the posture, it first and foremost speaks to the influx of not only Chinese porcelain vessels but also decorative artworks, such as statuettes circulating in Amsterdam. The juxtaposition of the Christian triptych and the Chinese figurine indicates the emerging interplay between Western and non-Western objects, which aims to unlock metaphors. This artistic approach aligns with Rembrandt’s aesthetic inclinations, as evidenced by his frequent use of Japanese paper and Oriental turbans in his portraits and genre compositions and the presence of imported Asian textiles in his works. Additionally, some of Rembrandt’s oeuvres display direct influences from Asian, specifically Mughal art, which also may explain his familiarity with Chinese figurines.⁴¹ The inclusion of the Chinese statue as one of the symbols of the connoisseur’s identity mirrors Rembrandt’s artistic vision and his ability to integrate different cultural

³⁹ Rembrandt van Rijn, Abraham Francen, “apothecary,” c. 1657, paper, etching/drypoint, height 157 mm × width 209 mm, Rijksmuseum, RP-P-OB-535, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en/collection/ RP-P-OB-535>.

⁴⁰ Rembrandt van Rijn (1606–1669), Abraham Francen, “Apothecary,” 1657–1658, Etching, drypoint, and engraving, 156 x 208 mm (6 1/8 x 8 3/16 in.), Fine Arts Museum of San Francisco, 1963.30.127, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.famsf.org/artworks/abraham-francen-apothecary>.

⁴¹ Zirka Z Filipczak, “Rembrandt and the Body Language of Mughal Miniatures.” *Nederlands Kunsthistorisch Jaarboek (NKJ) / Netherlands Yearbook for History of Art* 58 (2007), 163.

elements into his works, indicating his aesthetic choices and the vogue for Oriental art in the Dutch art market of the time. Besides, the representation of the Western connoisseur interacting with art objects and goods from overseas highlights the encounter of the Western and Eastern cultures, underscoring the growing importance of Chinese culture in the Western perception of Asia and the West's self-image of the explorer and illuminator. This suggests that the Chinese commodity was no longer perceived as a mysterious and unattainable object of the divine or reserved for royalty but rather as a symbol for the intellectual middle class to decode their identity and display their intelligence.

Spanish Baroque and Chinaware

In the sixteenth century, Spain witnessed the rise of celebrated collectors of chinaware. Interestingly, the Spanish classified Oriental art objects as *bujerías*, or knick-knacks (*miudezas* in Portuguese), and listed them as such in documents, porcelains being lumped together with lacquered writing desks or boxes, semi-precious stones, jewelry, fans, ivory; porcelain and other exotica were even referred to as *bagatelas*—"mere trifles."⁴² This valuation contradicts the high regard granted to Chinese commodities in Northern Europe.

Francisco de Zurbarán (1598–1664), one of the key figures in Spanish Baroque and the leading painter in Seville, nicknamed "Spanish Caravaggio" for his *tenebroso* compositions, created a set of still-life compositions and genre paintings with the chinaware. In his famous painting of a Carthusian refectory,⁴³ he intensely reflects the ideal of this order of hermit monks: simplicity, sobriety, and quiet contemplation. A Chinese blue-and-white porcelain bowl is turned down on its rims. Two other chinaware jars create a sense of rhythm, corresponding to the overall mood of contemplation and spiritual tranquility.

The above-discussed tradition set up by Benaglio and Mantegna to use Chinese porcelain to indicate the sacral character of the narrative is extended in Zurbarán's "Sleeping Child Mary (1640–1650),"⁴⁴ which reflects the mid-seventeenth century monastic tales of the Virgin's childhood. Mary is depicted as sleeping soundly, lost in a spiritual dream, draped in a

⁴² Cinta Krahe, *Chinese Porcelain in Habsburg Spain*, Madrid, Centro de Estudios Europa Hispánica, 2016.

⁴³ Francisco de Zurbarán, (b. 1598, Fuente de Cantos, d. 1664, Madrid), "St Hugo of Grenoble in the Carthusian Refectory," c. 1633, oil on canvas, 102 x 168 cm, Museo de Bellas Artes, Seville.

⁴⁴ Francisco de Zurbarán, "The Virgin Mary as a Child, Asleep," 1640–1650, Oil on canvas, 40 9/16 x 35 7/16 in (103 x 90 cm), Galerie Caneso, Milan, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.caneso.art/artworkdetail/779958/0/zurbaran-the-virgin-mary-as-a-child>.

crimson robe, symbolizing both love and royalty, and clutching a blue mantle, representative of hope and fidelity. The decor of the room is unassuming, with only a simple rush-bottomed chair and a Chinese bowl containing an arrangement of flowers: a rose, symbolizing love, a five-petalled red carnation, emblematic of the five wounds of Christ, and a lily, indicating virgin purity. As Cinta Krahe confirms, the depicted Kraak bowl is identical to a sample from the San Diego shipwreck, dated around 1600.⁴⁵

Juan de Zurbarán (1620–1649) continued the current tradition of his father, featuring expensive Chinese export bowls with the precise, sensuous application of paint and dramatic lighting.⁴⁶ His “Still Life of Lemons” (circa 1643–1649)⁴⁷ presents a highly symbolic composition with the porcelain bowl, which has a distinctive repeating motif of a deer; it was made in China for export and reappeared in another painting attributed to Francisco de Zurbarán, suggesting that it was in his studio. An example of the bowl, salvaged from a galleon that sunk off the Philippines in 1600, is in the Museo Naval, Madrid. In the current composition, a goldfinch perches on the edge of a Chinese porcelain bowl filled with water; the water and lily both refer to the purity of the Virgin Mary. Therefore, it’s yet another instance when the Chinese porcelain is implied as a symbol and alludes to the Mother of God, underlining her chastity, and typifies the Spanish Baroque approach to the usage of chinaware as a compositional element.

Conclusion

The cultural phenomena of Orientalism and Chinoiserie were preceded by the widespread popularity of Chinese porcelain and figurines as emblematic representations of the East for Western audiences, collectors, connoisseurs, and artistic communities. These commodities fostered an appreciation for Chinese artistry, aesthetic curiosity, and consumerism, yet their proliferation also reinforced Western perceptions of ownership and superiority over Eastern cultures.

⁴⁵ Cinta Krahe, *Chinese Porcelain in Habsburg Spain*, 272.

⁴⁶ Juan de Zurbarán, “Flowers and Fruit in a Chinese Bowl,” circa 1645, c. 1640–1650, oil on canvas, 82.6 × 108.6 cm (32 1/2 × 42 3/4 in.), Art Institute of Chicago, 1947.511, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.artic.edu/artists/42406/francisco-de-zurbaran>

⁴⁷ Juan de Zurbarán, “Still Life of Lemons,” about 1643–1649, oil on canvas, 81.4 × 108.5 cm, The National Gallery, London, NG6669, accessed April 24, 2024, <https://www.nationalgallery.org.uk/paintings/juan-de-zurbaran-still-life-with-lemons-in-a-wicker-basket>

Chinese ceramic goods, originating in non-Western societies, didn't influence the style and the formal qualities of Western art, as the artists who painted them remained "Western" in their application of the paint, the artistic pursuit of realistic depictions, three-dimensionality, the illusion of depth, and the dramatic lighting, and compositional arrangements.

Nonetheless, the introduction of China-made porcelain to Europe opened up new possibilities for the subject matter of European painting. This development allowed artists to convey multilayered, symbolic ideas, allegories, and metaphors, leading to a greater complexity and depth of meaning in their work. In addition to this, it introduced new color combinations and a love for exotic details and ornamentation, which lent an exquisite touch to their art pieces. These tendencies created fertile ground for the development of the still-life genre in the following centuries, as well as the flourishing of movements in Western art that were highly inspired by Asian commodities, culture, and philosophy.

The continuity of Western tradition in the inclusion of Chinese ceramics in visual art monuments is reflected in the use of Chinese blue-and-white porcelain to allude to the purity and divinity of the Christian protagonists in the Italian Renaissance (Benaglio, Mantegna), further extended by the Spanish Baroque artists (Zurbarán, *The Virgin Mary as a Child, Asleep*). However, within the same tradition, a change was observed in the employment of Chinese commodities as compositional compounds by the Dutch Baroque artists (Willem Kalf). In this instance, the use of Chinese commodities was not to convey biblical overtones and Christian allegories but rather as symbols of economic power and the global circulation of Asian goods. Furthermore, the Dutch Golden Age painters were among the first Western artists to execute Chinese items alongside and in various combinations with other precious imported objects of the time. Nevertheless, the novel interpretation within the framework of the tradition was introduced by Rembrandt van Rijn. He is regarded as one of the pioneering Western artists who used not only a Chinese ginger jar but also a China-made art object—a figurine—as an item to unlock the identity of an art collector and connoisseur. This approach was to be enhanced in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

Bibliography

1. Anderson, Jaynie. "The Provenance of Bellini's Feast of the Gods and a New/Old Interpretation." *Studies in the History of Art* 45 (1993): 264–287, repro. no. 10.
2. Andrade, Tonio. "The Dutch East India Company in Global History: A Historiographical Reconnaissance." In *The Dutch and English East India Companies: Diplomacy, Trade and Violence in Early Modern Asia*, edited by Adam Clulow and Tristan Mostert. Amsterdam University Press, 2018.
3. Cinta Krahe, *Chinese Porcelain in Habsburg Spain*, Madrid, Centro de Estudios Europa Hispánica, 2016.
4. Degenhardt, Jane Hwang. "Cracking the Mysteries of 'China': China(Ware) in the Early Modern Imagination." *Studies in Philology* 110, no. 1 (2013): 132–167.
5. Downs, Joseph. "The China Trade and Its Influences." *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin* 36, no. 4 (1941): 84–95.
6. Filipczak, Zirka Z. "Rembrandt and the Body Language of Mughal Miniatures." *Nederlands Kunsthistorisch Jaarboek (NKJ) / Netherlands Yearbook for History of Art* 58 (2007): 162–87.
7. Finlay, Robert. "China, the China, the West, and World History in Joseph Needham's 'Science and Civilisation in China.'" *Journal of World History* 11, no. 2 (2000): 265–303.
8. GERRITSEN, ANNE and STEPHEN MCDOWALL. "Material Culture and the Other: European Encounters with Chinese Porcelain, ca. 1650-1800." *Journal of World History* 23, no. 1 (2012): 87–113.
9. Grisebach, Lucius. *Willem Kalf, 1619-1693*. Berlin: Gebr Mann Verlag, 1974.
10. Harrison-Hall, Jessica. *Catalog of late Yuan and Ming ceramics in the British Museum*. London: British Museum, 2001.
11. Hochstrasser, Julie. *Still Life and Trade in the Dutch Golden Age*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2007.
12. Kipling, J.M. *Kipling Boy Stories*. Chicago: Rand, McNally & Company, 1916.
13. La Farge, John. "Tradition and Art." *The Irish Monthly* 71, no. 843 (1943): 372–78.
14. Le Corbeiller, Clare. "A Medici Porcelain Pilgrim Flask." *The J. Paul Getty Museum Journal* 16 (1988): 119–126.
15. Le Corbeiller, Clare. "German Porcelain of the Eighteenth Century." *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin* 47, no. 4 (1990): 1–56.
16. Lion-Goldschmidt, Daisy. "Les Porcelaines Chinoises Du Palais de Santos." *Arts Asiatiques* 39 (1984): 5–72.
17. Mack, Rosamond E. "Patterned Silks," in *Bazaar to Piazza: Islamic Trade and Italian Art, 1300-1600*. Berkeley: the University of California Press, 2002.
18. Pope, John A. and A. G. Wenley. *China* (Smithsonian Institution War Background Studies Number Twenty). Washington, D. C.: Smithsonian Inst., 1944.
19. Said, Edward W. *Orientalism*. New York: Pantheon Books, 1978.
20. Smith, Jeffrey Chipps. "The 2010 Josephine Waters Bennett Lecture: Albrecht as Collector." *Renaissance Quarterly* 64, no. 1 (2011): 1–49.
21. Van Thiel, P. J. J. "Een Stilleven Door Pieter Claesz." *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum* 23, no. 2 (1975), 119–121.
22. Zerubavel, Eviatar. "The Standardization of Time: A Sociohistorical Perspective." *American Journal of Sociology* 88, no. 1 (1982): 1–23.

“Cave Motifs in Chinese and Armenian Literature: Portals to the Mystical World and Their Literary Legacy”

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Abstract: Caves as abodes of supernatural forces are significant in traditional Chinese religions, specifically Taoism. In Taoist sources, caves are described as places where or through which a chosen individual gains access to a world entirely distinct from the real one. Caves also serve as representative symbols of the otherworld in Armenian traditions. However, they do not always conceal a blissful realm within them, as is often the case in Taoist writings. This article explores caves as symbols of the heavenly and blissful worlds in Taoist works, and Armenian caves as locations harboring supernatural powers.

Keywords: cave, Taoism, immortality, Chinese Literature, Armenian folklore

Introduction: Exploring the Cultural Significance of Caves in Different Societies

Across diverse cultures, folk stories, legends, and myths enshroud the profound significance of caves. These enigmatic natural formations have served multifaceted roles throughout history, encompassing religious, ritualistic, and aesthetic functions. Notably, within the tapestries of Armenian and Chinese cultures, an array of traditions, myths, and behaviors intertwine with the significance of mountains and caves.

The narratives associated with caves predominantly intertwine with the nomenclature and geographical positioning of specific mountains, given the habitual proximity of caves to the bases, slopes, or summits of these landforms. For instance, a group of revered mountains in China holds sacred status, invoking veneration and distinct reverence among the Chinese populace (Mount Tai 泰山, Mount Hua 华山, Mount Heng 恒山, Mount Song 嵩山 and Heng Mountain 衡山). Integral to these mountains are the caves that reside within them, often embellished with temples at their entrances or adorned with statues depicting figures from Buddhist or Taoist traditions.

Taoism, an influential philosophical and religious tradition in Chinese culture, venerates mountains as sanctuaries, offering solace from the rigors of civilization. These natural landscapes symbolize freedom and seclusion, providing a refuge where individuals seek medicinal herbs and other substances. Moreover, these mountains harbor the essential components requisite for Taoist alchemical practices, including mineral resources and precious

stones such as emeralds, crucial for formulating elixirs promising immortality and eternal youth. Notably, the caves of these mountains are believed to be inhabited by immortals¹.

In the Armenian culture, mountains, stones, and caves, exemplified by landmarks such as Maruta Mountain, Masis Mountain, Aragats, Mrav, Nemrut, and Andok, hold a central place in the spiritual traditions of the Armenian people². Notably, Mount Nemrut attained prominence as a site of worship, initially dedicated to the god Khaldi and subsequently evolving to revere the deities Aramazd and Vahagn. Legends surrounding the caves of Mount Masis, conversely, associate them with malevolent spirits and enigmatic phenomena.

This article embarks on an exploration of several Chinese and Armenian traditions and narratives concerning caves. Primarily, it demonstrates the interconnectedness of these narratives and, through comparative analysis, elucidates the role and significance of caves in the cultural lives of both nations. The discourse culminates in the revelation that while the external characteristics of these cave stories diverge, they share common motifs. Foremost among these shared motifs is the centrality of caves as places of religious veneration, inextricably linked with various rituals or revered figures. Within the scope of this article, we refrain from delving into the Christian connotations of caves, as such an exploration constitutes a complex and extensive field of study.

For comparative insights, Armenian folk tales, such as "Little Mher" (Փոքր Մհեր) and "Artavazd and Artashes" (Արտավազդ և Արտաշէս) are juxtaposed with Chinese sources, including Taoist narratives and the renowned work Taohua yuanji 桃花源記 ("Peach Blossom Spring") by the eminent Chinese author Tao Yuanming 陶淵明 (365–42).

This article employs a multifaceted approach, combining analytical, comparative, and cross-cultural methodologies. The analysis hinges on a synthesis of primary narratives, traditions, and stories from these two distinct cultures, showcasing the interplay and connections within their respective cave lore. The multifaceted methods employed allow for a comprehensive examination of the stories' cultural and symbolic significance, uncovering the shared motifs and distinctions that exist between these narratives.

¹ Schafer Edward H., *Mao Shan in T'ang Times* (Boulder:SSCR Monographs no.1.rev.ed. 1989), 22-24.

² For more details see Samvel Dilanyan, *Armenian Sacred Mountains* (Yerevan: Edit Print, 2012).

Cave Motifs in Chinese Literature: A Portal to the Mystical

The presence of cave narratives in Chinese religious and artistic works bears profound cultural and spiritual significance. Caves, known as *dong* 洞 in Chinese, play a pivotal role within the tapestry of Chinese culture, intrinsically intertwined with Taoism and Buddhism. These natural formations often functioned as hermitages not only for Taoist sages but also for Buddhist monks, offering solitude for spiritual contemplation.

Beyond their role as sanctuaries for spiritual reflection, caves held an additional, enigmatic significance. They were seen as gateways to a world concealed from ordinary human sight, inhabited by immortal beings central to Chinese folklore and belief. In the realms of Taoism, caves serve as transcendental passages, connecting the terrestrial and the supernatural.

Taoist tales concerning caves frequently share recurring motifs, typically featuring a protagonist, often accompanied by an animal companion, notably a dog. These narratives, though possessing common elements, were crafted with varying objectives in mind. One such illustration of these tales can be found within the *Liexian Zhuan* 列仙传 ("Biography of the Immortals"), attributed to Liu Xiang 刘向 (77-622 BC). A narrative called *Hanzi* 寒子 recounts the journey of a man named Hanzi, a resident of the Shu 蜀 region, who inadvertently follows the canine into a cave. Their exploration within the cave extends for over ten days, eventually leading them to a realm adorned with palaces and pavilions embellished with lush pines and vibrant blooms, and guarded by immortal sentinels.

In this realm, a woman presents Hanzi with a missive and a collection of elixirs, instructing him to deliver them to Lord Qiao 乔公, the Magistrate of Chengdu 成都. Enclosed in the missive are fish, which, following a year submerged in water, metamorphose into dragons. Impelled by this mystical encounter, Lord Qiao dispatches Hanzi back to the cave mountain, commencing a cycle of traversing between the mortal and immortal dimensions, a journey undertaken more than a hundred times. Hanzi, over time, establishes a permanent residence within the mountain, occasionally descending to safeguard his family and tribe. Recognizing his transcendent stature, the people of Shu constructed a temple at the cave's entrance in his

honor. This act propels the veneration of Hanzi, with his cult expanding to the southern regions, offering promises of protection and happiness³.

This narrative underscores the cave's role as a liminal space, bridging two worlds and concealing a mystical realm of wonder and inaccessibility. The protagonist's serendipitous discovery of the cave portal enables his transitory passage between these realms, ultimately leading to his attainment of immortality. Moreover, the story embodies a more profound significance: the ritualistic connection between the mortal and immortal domains, exemplified by Hanzi's apotheosis as an object of worship, promising prosperity and protection through the act of veneration⁴. We may say cave narratives within Taoist lore serve as symbolic portals to the transcendent, encapsulating the essence of the human desire to bridge the ordinary and the mystical.

These narratives often serve as vehicles for conveying the mystical. Among the earliest accounts, we find the "grotto passage" from the late 3rd to early 4th century Taoist canon, known as *lingbao wufu jing xu* 靈寶五符經序 ("Scripture of Five Talismans of the Numinous Treasure"). This account is a seminal example of the "cave-paradise" motif, recounting the journey of a Daoist seeker dispatched by Emperor HeLu 闍閻 of the Wu Kingdom 吳 on a quest to discover a heavenly scripture hidden within a cave beneath Lake Tai 太. This tale distinguishes itself by its fantastical depiction of the cave, replete with dragons, phoenixes, miraculously quenching waters, and other wonders. The protagonist, an accomplished recluse, has attained the *dao* 道 (way) and, through sacred rituals, retrieves the hallowed scripture from the cave, subsequently presenting it to the emperor⁵.

Such Taoist narratives, replete with enchanting cave paradises, would leave an indelible mark on later Chinese writers and artists. Among the most renowned literary works influenced by these traditions is "The Peach Blossom Spring" by Tao Yuanming. In this masterpiece of Chinese literature, Tao Yuanming takes his readers on an imaginary journey into a cave, positioning the description of the cave paradise as the focal point of the narrative.

³ Zhang Jinling and Chen Manming, ed. *Xinyi Liexianzuan* 列仙傳 (A new translated Biographies of Arrayed Immortals), Taipei: Sanmin shuju, 1997, 226.

⁴ Sing-chen and Chiang, Lydia. "Visions of happiness: Daoist utopias and Grotto paradises in Early and Medieval Chinese Tales," *Utopian studies* 20(1):97-120 (Penn State University Press, 2009), 103.

⁵ Stephen Bokenkamp, *Early Daoist Scriptures* (Berkeley CA: University of California Press, 1997), 377-98.

Tao Yuanming's work is distinguished by its portrayal of a blissful world concealed within a cave, a world akin to the sanctuary sought by the Daoist seekers of ancient tales. The hero embarks on a journey that transcends the physical realm, venturing into the cave, and unveiling a utopian realm that exists beyond the mundane world. It was Tao Yuanming who pioneered the concept of the cave-paradise, placing it at the narrative forefront, and providing an evocative glimpse into the mystical and the extraordinary. The story narrates that during the reign period Tai yuan 太元 (326-97) of the Jin 晉, a fisherman from Wuling 武陵 wandered along a stream and stumbled upon a grove of peach trees stretching along its banks. Following the grove, he found a spring and a hill with a small opening. Curious, he entered and emerged into an open field. In this place, the fisherman saw some kind of heavenly world with beautiful scenery, imposing buildings, and people working in the fields.

In the sequel, it is mentioned that these people arrived during the Qin dynasty 秦 (221-207 BC) amid times of chaos, and they have remained there since, isolated from the outside world. A fisherman stays briefly, leaves markers along his path for a potential return, and conveys all this to the ruler. The ruler dispatches men to locate this hidden realm following the markers, but they are unsuccessful in finding the concealed location⁶.

When comparing these three stories, we observe several important points. Firstly, the cave hides a world distinct from reality, a paradisiacal realm, signifying that it is a place filled with wonders or a gateway to the celestial world. Secondly, the cave, along with the world concealed within it, is not visible and accessible to everyone; not everyone can discover the cave and enter the new world. Thirdly, the protagonists in each story encounter the cave unexpectedly, highlighting chance as the means of discovery rather than deliberate search or intention. Lastly, there is the presence of a ritualistic or cultic element.

In all three stories, the heroes discover the cave-paradise purely by accident. This highlights one of the fundamental Taoist principles, the use of the concept of wuwei 无为 (inactivity), which implies naturalness and spontaneity. The characters do not access the cave through mystical incantations but rather stumble upon its entrance by chance, which can only be found by those not actively seeking it.

⁶ Anthology of Chinese Literature, Volume I: From Early Times to Fourteenth century, ed. by Cyril Birch (New York: Grove Press, 1965), 167-68.

Regarding "The Peach Blossom Spring," it is worth noting that the author does not solely focus on moral criticism of the corrupt world they inhabit. They also express a desire for a place where people can live, akin to those who took refuge in the cave in their story. The author emphasizes the Taoist concept of Laozi's ideal society model⁷, known as *xiaoguo guamin* 小国寡民 (a small country with few people). This downplays the significance of Taoist esoteric practices and reinterprets the cave-paradise stories, making them more appealing to the educated class familiar with Taoist philosophical teachings and yearning to escape the chaotic real world⁸.

The existence of numerous Taoist texts written about *dongtian* 洞天 (cave-paradise) worlds has led Chinese researchers to believe that, in any case, people in times genuinely believed in the existence of an otherworldly immortal realm⁹. Li Jianguo 李劍國 agreed with Lu Xun's 魯迅 quotation that Tao Yuanming "did not superstitiously believe in demons and gods,"¹⁰ however Tao Yuanming had a clear fascination with spiritual beings¹¹. Other researchers interpret it as a real place where people sought shelter from external threats and tried to find the exact location where that cave-paradise could be located. Chen Yinke 陳寅恪 and Tang Changru 唐長孺 provide detailed speculations about the possible location of the "Peach Blossom" site¹².

The Taoist theory of heaven and earth originated during the Eastern Jin Dynasty (AD 317-420) and reached its final form during the late Tang (618-907) and Five Dynasties periods (907-960). Tao Hongjing 陶弘景 (456–536) from the Six Dynasties, Sima Chengzhen 司马承祯 (639–735) from the Tang Dynasty, and Du Guangting 杜光庭 (850-933) from the late Tang and Five Dynasties can be regarded as representative figures in the three important stages of

⁷ Sing-chen & Lydia Chiang. "Visions of happiness", 115.

⁸ Lee Fongmao 李豐楙. 洞天與內景: 西元二至四世紀江南道教的內向游觀(Grotto Heavens and Inner Realms: The Inner Visualization Meditations in Jiangnan Daoism from Second to Fourth Century), *Dong Hwa Journal of Chinese Studies* 9 (2009), 157-197.

⁹ Chan, Timothy; Wai, Keung. "A Tale of Two Worlds: The Late Tang Poetic Presentation of the Romance of the Peach Blossom." (*Font T'oung Pao* 94.4, 2008), p. 209-245; Mark Meulenbeld, "The Peach Blossom Spring's Long History as a Sacred Site in Northern Hunan", *T'oung Pao* 107.1-2, (2021), 1-39.

¹⁰ Lu Xun 魯迅, *Zhongguo xiaoshuo shilue* 中国小说史略(A Brief History of Chinese Fiction), Shanghai: Beixin shuju, [1925] 1936.

¹¹ Li Jianguo 李劍國, *Tangqian zhiguai xiaoshuo shi* 唐前志怪小說史(A History of Strange Novels Before Tang Dynasty), Beijing: Renmin, [1984] 2011, 466.

¹² Chen Yinke 陳寅恪, "Taohuayuan ji pangzheng 桃花源記旁證," *Tsing Hua Journal of Chinese Studies* 11.1 (1936): 79-88; Tang Changru 唐長孺, "Du 'Taohuayuan ji pangzheng' zhiyi 《讀〈桃花源記旁證〉質疑》," in *Wei Jin Nanbeichaoshi lunji xubian* 魏晉南北朝史論集續編, Beijing: Sanlian, 1959, 163-177.

development of this theory¹³. The best explanation of the concept of Dongtian 洞天 can be found in the early Qing dynasty classic *Ziyang zhenren neizhuan* 紫阳真人内传 («Inner Transmission of Zi Yang Immortals»). According to some interpretations of the text, dongtian has two meaning. Broadly speaking, dongtian encompasses the sky (heaven), mountain caves, and empty spaces within human heads. In Taoist understanding, these three realms are believed to be inhabited by various levels of true men and immortals, including celestial gods, earthly immortals, and personal gods. The narrow interpretation of dongtian is confined to mountain caves. However, these are not ordinary caves as commonly understood, but rather interpreted with religious, and geographical significance. In Taoist theories of sacred places, dongtian refers to various caves of different sizes¹⁴.

Caves of Culture and Spirit: Exploring Armenian Traditions

In Armenian culture, caves were not only associated with Christianity, serving as places for monks to practice hermitage but also played a significant role in Armenian legends. They often concealing an invisible realm—another world or the underworld—where evil heroes were chained or heroes voluntarily were locked away.

Armenian folklore, myths, and traditions contain numerous stories related to the use of caves and their cultural importance. Two different approaches to caves can be found in the Armenian folk epic "Sasna Tsrer" and the legend of "Artavazd and Artashes." In the "Sasna Tsrer" epic, the main character of the chapter of "Little Mher." Little Mher voluntarily imprisons himself within a cave, he will come out from the cave only when world will be transformed. In the legend of "Artavazd and Artashes," king Artavazd is forcibly confined in a cave and will only emerge at the end of the world.

According to Armenian historian Moses of Khoren's epic tale, Artavazd is locked in a cave, bound with an iron chain, and he attempts to escape the underground world with the aid of dogs to bring about the world's end. However, blacksmiths strengthen their shackles with their hammering¹⁵. According to versions reported by historians Yeznik and Vardan Areveltsi, Artavazd is confined alive in the caves of Mount Masis by dragons or demons. Should he

¹³ Zhang Guangbao 张广保. *Daojiao de dongtianfudi lilunde qiyuan ji lishi fazhan* 道教的洞天福地理论的起源及历史发展 [The Origin and Historical Development of the Taoist Theory of Cave and Blessed Land]. 《道家的根本道论与道教的心性学》, Bashu shushe, 2008, 588-648. Also see Li Jianguo 李剑国, *Tangqian zhiguai xiaoshuo shi* 唐前志怪小说史, 466-480.

¹⁴ Zhang Guangbao. *Daojiao de dongtianfudi lilunde qiyuan ji lishi fazhan*, 590-1.

¹⁵ Moses of Khoren, *History of Armenians*. (Original text by M. Abegheyan and S. Yartunyan, Tpkhis, 1913), B.

escape, he would bring about the world's destruction or emerge someday to do so¹⁶. In the continuation of the myth, it is said that dogs lick their chains, causing them to weaken. To prevent his escape, blacksmiths strike the stone slab with a hammer one to three times on New Year's Eve or the first day of the new year.

This myth about King Artavazd has been examined by numerous researchers, as it provides insights into the ritual practices of ancient Armenians. Within this myth, we can discern the origins of the New Year ritual and its significance¹⁷. As characterized by Harutyunyan, "Artavazd-Shitar appears as a world-destroying monster, a dragon representing the chaotic forces of the earth. Blacksmiths, seen as representatives of the deity who establish cosmic order, battle against him in a ritual ceremony. At the start of the New Year, they repair the world that has neared the brink of decay at the end of the old year."¹⁸ The cave serves as a location for concealing evil forces, specifically Artavazd, to prevent him from bringing about the world's destruction. The eschatological beliefs of ancient Armenians are also embedded in this myth.

Caves in Epics: Eschatological Themes and Shelter from Chaos

In the Armenian folk epic, an alternative portrayal of cave use can be observed, tied to eschatological ideas and beyond. This narrative, exemplified by Little Mher's self-imposed seclusion in a cave with plans to emerge later, showcases significant differences from similar tales. While both narratives exhibit eschatological and ritualistic elements, variations exist in the reasons for the heroes' seclusion and the conditions for their emergence.

For instance, in stories from the Mshō typological group of the epic, where the myth of Mher is present, Little Mher's emergence is often linked with the impending transformation of the world. His exit from the cave is tethered to a specific societal indicator: an extraordinary growth in the size of grains, such as barley and wheat: "When the barley grain reached the size of a nut (or 'when the barley was the size of a cashew nut'), only Mher would emerge from the cave"¹⁹.

Comparing this with "Peach Blossom Spring," where people willingly seclude themselves in a cave, fleeing the real world to create their idyllic haven away from the chaos caused by rulers' wars, a similarity emerges. However, the inhabitants of this secluded community in the Taoist tale have no desire to leave the cave. We can draw a parallel with Little Mher. In both cases,

¹⁶ Eznkai Koghbatsvoi, *Sects*. (Tiflis, 1914), A, IE.

¹⁷ Sargis Harutyunyan, *The Armenian epic and the world epic heritage*. (Yerevan, 2014), 14.

¹⁸ Sargis Harutyunyan, *The Armenian epic and the world epic heritage*, 14.

¹⁹ The translation is mine, see Armenian folk epic «Davit of Sassoon» (Yerevan, 1961) B I, 44, 101, 102, 195, 246, G 55, 441.

the cave acts as a shield, protecting those within from the outside world. Weary of the injustices and turmoil of the world, Little Mher chooses to isolate himself in a cave, planning to reemerge only if the world undergoes change. Similarly, in Tao's narrative, the people find immense joy in their cave dwelling and are uninterested in leaving, though they eagerly accept newcomers seeking refuge from the chaotic external world.

Cave Narratives: Contrasting Perspectives on Abundance and Purpose

The narrative of "Little Mher" has received extensive scholarly attention, with studies by M. Abeghyan, H. Tumanyan, S. Harutyunyan and others. Researchers have compared Mher's character with similar heroes from different cultures, highlighting commonalities and distinctions.

In the context of S. Harutyunyan's observation that "the people desire abundance and social welfare, often expressed through the quantity of wheat,²⁰" it becomes evident that differing cultural and philosophical ideals shape the criteria for prosperity. While Taoist ideals prioritize simplicity, scarcity, and essentials for a happy life in a small, harmonious society²¹, the Armenian folk epic emphasizes grandeur and abundance as indicators of well-being.

Little Mher's decision to seclude himself in a cave in the Armenian epic carries profound motivations. Cursed by his father and rendered immortal, he is disinherited. The instability of the ground beneath him, feigned and desecrated, prompts him to question his relevance to this world. This introspective moment is illustrated in the epic when Mher tests his innocence by striking a stone with his sword. According to Shahverdyan, Mher's concern for all of humanity, coupled with his inability to rectify an unjust world, compels him to withdraw from that world.²²

In Taoist stories, heroes do not always find themselves in caves by happenstance. In the first and second tales, individuals actively seek a sacred book whose principles, if adhered to, would restore order in the world. Little Mher, on the other hand, departs from this world, leaving the task of world transformation to future generations. In Taoist works, religious figures prioritize following their teachings and adhering to the rules of their sacred texts as a means to establish harmony and order in the world.

²⁰ Sargis Harutyunyan, *The Armenian epic and the world epic heritage*, 20-21.

²¹ Laozi 80

²² Gayane Shahverdyan, *From Little Mher to Christ* (Yerevan, 2001), 110.

Conclusion

In the comparative analysis of Chinese and Armenian cave narratives, it becomes evident that despite differing purposes, motivations, and central themes, there are common features shared by these traditions. Within these works, several essential ideas are emphasized.

Firstly, the significance of the cave is a recurring theme in both Armenian and Chinese narratives. The cave is portrayed as a place with a deceptively simple exterior, concealing a mysterious and supernatural world within. Through caves, individuals in these narratives find themselves in alternate realms, be it the blissful and heavenly worlds in Chinese stories or the underworld, the detention site of malevolent forces, or the sanctuary of virtuous heroes in Armenian tales. Notably, descriptions of Chinese Taoist fantasy worlds, sacred books, and secret formulas are absent from Armenian traditions.

As a concluding observation, the caves serve as gateways to the supernatural, and those who enter them often acquire or already possess supernatural qualities. In Chinese Taoist stories, people may find the key to immortality, becoming immortal upon arrival, while in Armenian legends, characters like Little Mher are already supernatural beings capable of living eternally within the cave. Conversely, figures like Artavazd are presented as supernatural and malevolent forces, and only the cave can contain their power, preventing them from emerging and wreaking upon the world. These narratives reflect the eschatological ideas of ancient Armenians, encompassing notions of world destruction and transformation, while the Chinese tales embody the Taoist pursuit of an ideal, heavenly world.

In both cases, the cave stories outline the emergence and regulation of a cult or ritual. As we have seen, in the case of Armenia, it is connected with the Navasard festival and the cult of the dying-resurrecting deity, while in the case of China, it is associated with the emergence of the cult of Taoist saints.

In several Armenian folk tales, gold and precious stones are hidden in caves. Surprisingly, much like in Taoist stories, these treasures are discovered by a random passerby. For example, in one of the folk tales related to the Armenian Cave of Temapoos, a villager happened upon a hole leading to the cave in the mountain. He found numerous precious stones and gold inside, put them in a bag, placed it on a donkey, and left. However, upon realizing he had left his walking stick in the cave, he returned. Unfortunately, the time for the cave door to open had passed, and the cave closed, trapping him inside. The donkey returned home with its load.

In a manner somewhat akin to the tales of the Taoist mystical world but not entirely equivalent, there were also stories among the Armenian people. For instance, the legend of the widow of Artsvakayr, located on the south side of Moks, tells of Huri-fairies living in the cave. They supposedly emerge from the cave on the night of funerals and dance in the natural surroundings, with the cave said to hold many riches and treasures.

In all Chinese and Armenian works, the wealth stored in the cave cannot be taken out; it cannot become the property of the outside world. If someone manages to remove these treasures in any way, they must return to the cave voluntarily or by force.

In summary, caves play a significant role in both Armenian and Chinese narratives as a location, a crossroads, or a boundary that separates the real world from the supernatural realm. Beyond their function as passageways, caves also represent a supernatural and otherworldly dimension. In Chinese stories, caves have a positive connotation, serving as paradisiacal realms inhabited by benevolent supernatural forces and immortals. In Armenian folklore, caves hold a more passive and neutral position. What matters most is not the physical appearance or descriptions of the cave but the role ascribed to it; a cave is a mysterious place that shelters malevolent and other supernatural forces.

Bibliography

1. Abeghyan, Manuk. Countries: no. 8. Yerevan, 1985.
2. Adamyan, Anna. "The Taoist model of ideal social order." *Scientific Artsakh* no.3(18) (2023): 89-99.
3. *Anthology of Chinese Literature, Volume I: From Early Times to Fourteenth century*, ed. By Cyril Birch, New York: Grove Press, 1965.
4. Armenian folk epic «Davit of Sassoon». Yerevan, 1961.
5. Avetisyan, Satenik. "The Crow Stone of the Armenian Soul." *Granish*, last modified 26.12.2023, www.granish.org
6. Bokenkamp, Stephen. *Early Daoist Scriptures*. Berkeley CA: University of California Press, 1997.
7. Chan, Timothy; Wai, Keung. "A Tale of Two Worlds: The Late Tang Poetic Presentation of the Romance of the Peach Blossom", *Font T'oung Pao* 94.4 (2008).
8. Chen Yinke 陳寅恪, "Taohuayuan ji pangzheng 桃花源記旁證," *Tsing Hua Journal of Chinese Studies* 11.1 (1936): 79–88.
9. Dilanyan, Samvel. *Armenian Sacred Mountains*. Yerevan: Edit Print, 2012.
10. Eznkai Koghbatsvoi. *Sects*. Tiflis, 1914.
11. Harutyunyan, Sargis. *The Armenian epic and the world epic heritage*. Yerevan: National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Armenia, 2014.
12. Harutyunyan, Sargis. *Armenian mythology*. Beirut, 2000.
13. Khanalanyan, Aram. *Avandapatum*. Yerevan: Armenian SS GA publishing house, 1969.
14. Laozi, *DaodeJing*, <https://www.daodejing.org/>
15. Lee Fongmao 李豐楙. 洞天與內景: 西元二至四世紀江南道教的 內向游觀(Grotto Heavens and Inner Realms: The Inner Visualization Meditations in Jiangnan Daoism from Second to Fourth Century), *Dong Hwa Journal of Chinese Studies* 9 (2009).
16. Li Jianguo 李劍國. *Tangqian zhiguai xiaoshuo shi 唐前志怪小說史(A History of Strange Novels Before Tang Dynasty)*, Beijing: Renmin, [1984] 2011.
17. Lu Xun 魯迅, *Zhongguo xiaoshuo shilue 中國小說史略(A Brief History of Chinese Fiction)*, Shanghai: Beixin shuju, [1925] 1936.
18. Meulenbeld, Mark. "The Peach Blossom Spring's Long History as a Sacred Site in Northern Hunan." *T'oung Pao* 107.1-2, 2021.
19. Moses of Khoren. *History of Armenians*. Original text by M. Abeghyan and S. Yartunyan, Tpkhis, 1913.
20. Shahverdyan, Gayane. *From Little Mher to Christ*. Yerevan, 2001.
21. Schafer, Edward H. *Mao Shan in T'ang Times*. Boulder:SSCR Monographs no.1.rev.ed. 1989.
22. Sing-chen and Chiang, Lydia. "Visions of happiness: Daoist utopias and Grotto paradises in Early and Medieval Chinese Tales." *Utopian studies* 20.1, Penn State University Press, 2009.
23. Tang Changru 唐長孺, Du 'Taohuayuan ji pangzheng' zhiyi 《讀〈桃花源記旁證〉質疑》, in *Wei Jin Nanbeichaoshi lunji xubian 魏晉南北朝史論集續編*, Beijing:

- Sanlian, 1959, 163–177.
24. Tumanyan, Hovhannes. Complete collection. No.7, Yerevan, 1999.
 25. Verellen, Franciscus. The Beyond Within: Grotto-Heavens in Taoist Ritual and Cosmology. Cahiers d'Extrême-Asie Année, 1995, 8.
 26. Zhang Guangbao 张广保. Daojiao de dongtianfudi lilunde qiyuan ji lishi fazhan 道教的洞天福地理论的起源及历史发展(The Origin and Historical Development of the Taoist Theory of Cave and Blessed Land), 《道家的根本道论与道教的心性学》, Bashu shushe, 2008.
 27. Zhang Jinling and Chen Manming. ed. Xinyi Liexianzhuan 列仙传(A new translated Biographies of Arrayed Immortals), Taipei:Sanmin shuju, 1997.